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A finite element approach for solving the shallow water equation on the sphere

Diploma Thesis by

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Abstract

Diploma of Mathematics

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This diploma thesis presents the development and implementation of a finite element method for solving the nonlinear shallow water equations on the sphere. Starting from a derivation of the shallow water equations from the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations, both the vector-invariant and conservative formulations are examined in terms of their conservation properties, numerical stability, and suitability for finite element discretisation. The method employs a compatible finite element framework with elements and spaces on spherical grids, specifically the *Cubed- and Triangular Sphere*, addressing geometric challenges such as coordinate singularities and metric consistency. Numerical experiments using standard benchmarks, including Galewsky flow and Rossby-Haurwitz waves, validate the accuracy and efficiency of the approach. The implementation is carried out in Julia, building upon existing numerical frameworks. The results support the method's potential for extension to more complex geophysical models involving additional physical processes. The whole Julia implementation can be found here [SSK25].

Contents

Introduction	1
1 The Shallow Water Equations	3
1.1 Derivation of the Incompressible Navier-Stokes Equations	4
1.2 Derivation of the Shallow Water Equations	8
1.3 Shallow Water Equations	11
1.4 Linear and non-linear Shallow Water Equations	12
2 Finite Element Methods	19
2.1 Functional analytical Basics	19
2.2 Ritz- and Galerkin Method	20
2.3 Finite Elements	22
3 Finite Elements on the Sphere	27
3.1 Spherical Grid Construction	27
3.2 Galerkin Projection on the Manifold	29
3.3 Transformation of Nodal functions	31
3.4 Finite Elements	34
4 Discretisation and FE-implementation	41
4.1 Compatible finite element methods	41
4.2 Outlook Recovery	49
5 Numerical Experiments	53
5.1 Barotrophically Unstable Zonal Flow - Galewsky	54
5.2 Rossby-Haurwitz Waves	70
5.3 Modon Collision	77
5.4 Planar Bickley-Jet	79
6 Outlook	83
A Quadrature rules of triangular elements	85
B Grid-Output Refinement	87
Literature	89

List of Figures

1.1	Shallow Water Equation, definition of variables	8
1.2	Shallow Water Equation, flat bottom	13
2.1	Geometric Mapping from reference element	23
3.1	Cube-to-sphere transformation by RONCHI et al.	28
3.2	Schematic figure of Triangular Grid Construction	29
3.3	Triangular Grid on the Sphere	29
3.4	Construction of the Triangular Grid on the Sphere	29
3.5	Transformation between reference triangle and physical space . .	30
3.6	Two adjacent cells and shared edge	34
3.7	RT-elements	36
3.8	DG-elements	37
3.9	VecDG Construction vector-invariant form	38
4.1	Outlook Recovery, De-Rahm Complex	50
5.1	Head-to-head Galewsky vs. CGDycore.jl	56
5.2	Galewsky, vort. field, vector-invariant, Cubed Sphere	57
5.3	Galewsky, vort. field, vector-invariant, Triangular Sphere (flat) . .	58
5.4	Galewsky, vort. field, conservative, Cubed Sphere	59
5.5	Galewsky, height field, conservative, Cubed Sphere	60
5.6	Galewsky, zonal velocity field, conservative, Cubed Sphere	61
5.7	Galewsky, meridional velocity field, conservative, Cubed Sphere .	62
5.8	Galewsky, error vort. field, conservative, Triangular Sphere	63
5.9	Galewsky, vort. field, cons. vs vec.-inv., Cubed Sphere	64
5.10	Galewsky, vort. field, cons. vs. vec.-inv. more details, Cubed Sphere	65
5.11	Galewsky, vort. field, vec.-inv., Triangular vs Cubed Sphere (flat) .	67
5.12	Galewsky, vort. field, vector-invariant, cubed vs. triangular	68
5.13	Galewsky, vort. field, vector-invariant, Cubed Sphere, diff. fem order	69
5.14	Haurwitz, vort. field, vector-invariant, Triangular Sphere	71
5.15	Haurwitz, vort. field, vector-invariant, Triangular Sphere (flat) . .	72
5.16	Haurwitz, vort. field, conservative, Cubed Sphere	73
5.17	Haurwitz, vort. field, conservative, Cubed Sphere	74
5.18	Haurwitz, Height field, conservative, Triangular Sphere (flat) . . .	75
5.19	Haurwitz, velocity field, conservative, Triangular Sphere (flat) . .	76

5.20	Haurwitz, vort. field, vector-invariant more details, Triangular Sphere	77
5.21	Modon, vort. field, Cubed Sphere, Head-to-Head, Lin vs. CGDycore.jl	78
5.22	Bickley-Jet, Height- and Velocity field, conservative, Cubed Sphere	80
5.23	Bickley-Jet, comparison Quad and Triangular Grid	80
5.24	Bickley-Jet, vort. field, conservative vs. vector-invariant, Quad vs. Tri	81
A.1	Quadrature rule triangles, Kubatko	86
B.1	Triangle and quadrilateral refinement	87
B.2	Triangular grid with refine level 1	88

Introduction

Fluid dynamics plays a crucial role in understanding large-scale geophysical phenomena, including atmospheric circulation, ocean currents, and weather patterns. A particularly important model in this context is the shallow water equation (SWE), which captures the essential horizontal flow dynamics in a thin fluid layer. Due to its relative simplicity and physical relevance, the SWE has become a fundamental model in numerical weather prediction and climate modelling.

Solving the shallow water equations on a spherical domain is a non-trivial task. The curvature of the Earth introduces geometric complexity, and accurate long-term simulations require numerical methods that are stable, efficient, and capable of handling the irregularities of global grids. Finite element methods (FEM) have emerged as a powerful tool to address these challenges, offering flexibility in handling complex geometries and supporting high-order accuracy.

In this work, we develop and implement a finite element approach for solving the shallow water equations on the sphere. Our focus lies on both theoretical derivation and practical implementation. We begin with a detailed derivation of the shallow water equations from the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations, including linear and non-linear formulations. Subsequently, we introduce the finite element framework, including some functional analysis basics, and describe how these methods can be adapted to spherical geometries. Our focus is on two mathematically equivalent formulations of the nonlinear SWE. We analyse both the vector-invariant and conservative forms in detail, emphasising their respective advantages in terms of conservation properties, numerical stability, and ease of implementation within the finite element framework. The vector-invariant form is particularly well-suited for highlighting the rotational dynamics of the flow, while the conservative form ensures exact conservation of mass and momentum, which is crucial for long-term simulations and climate modelling. Both have advantages and disadvantages in certain test cases.

To implement these formulations on the sphere, we discuss the choice of appropriate finite element spaces, with a focus on mixed finite elements that satisfy discrete analogues of key physical properties such as mass conservation and potential vorticity conservation. We also address challenges arising from the spherical geometry, such as coordinate singularities at the poles and the need for metric-consistent discretisation.

The core part of this diploma thesis concerns the implementation of compatible finite element schemes on spherical grids. We investigate different grid constructions,

particularly the Cubed Sphere and Triangular Sphere, and analyse their impact on the solution quality. The numerical experiments include standard benchmark tests such as Galewsky flow, Rossby-Haurwitz waves, and modon collisions, which are used to assess the accuracy, stability, and efficiency of our method.

Since we are able to calculate not only on the spherical surface but also in a planar manifold. That's why we also have the option of simulating the Bickley jet. The implementation is carried out using a modern scientific computing language in the framework given by Julia. We are guided by the vision and ideas of LFRic (UK MET OFFICE), GUSTO (FIREDRAKE PROJECT) and use code and work from DR. OSWALD KNOTH as the starting point for our implementations. This work is an extension and simplified summary of the existing capabilities of the Fortran, Python and Matlab programmes named above. We are thus creating a general environment based on Julia, on which further methods can be built up. In addition, we use compatible finite element methods with Raviart-Thomas elements, discontinuous Galerkin elements, Lagrange elements and vector discontinuous Galerkin elements, in which the variables lie in function spaces that preserve the underlying geometric structure of the equations.

Our vision is to make different methods of finite volume, finite elements, etc., testable and comparable in one setting CGDYCORE.JL. In this thesis, we discuss not only the implementation but also the theoretical background.

Furthermore, we validate our method through a series of benchmark tests, including steady-state geostrophic balance, wave propagation, and nonlinear vortex dynamics, comparing our results with known analytical solutions and established numerical schemes. At the end, the implications of the findings are considered in the context of future developments in global atmospheric modelling. Potential extensions of the method include the incorporation of additional physical processes, such as moisture transport, stratification effects, and coupling with thermodynamic equations.

Chapter 1

The Shallow Water Equations

One of the most important equations in fluid dynamics are the Navier-Stokes equations. They are based on the assumption that the fluid, at the scale of interest, is a continuum, which describes a continuous substance rather than discrete particles. Besides this, another necessary assumption is that all fields of interest, including pressure, density, temperature, and so on, are at least weakly differentiable. The Navier-Stokes equations are derived from the fundamental physical principles of conservation of momentum and conservation of mass and energy. In some examples, we need to define a finite, so-called control volume, where our principles hold. Ω denotes the finite volume and its boundary surface by $\partial\Omega$.

The Shallow Water Equations (SWE) are a system of hyperbolic equations that describe a shallow layer of fluid. The domains are characterised by a vertical length scale h , which is significantly smaller than the horizontal length scale l , i.e. $h \ll l$. In other words, the thickness layer of the fluid is small compared to the horizontal length scale. So we can simplify by averaging over the depth. In summary, by integrating the 3D-Navier-Stokes equations, we can derive the SWE. However, it is crucial to note that our bottom topography does not change too rapidly, as referenced in WEIYAN [Wei92].

Applications

The SWE have a wide range of applications that extend far beyond their name's implication of being limited to shallow water bodies. The numerical solution of the SWE was one of the early applications of digital computers. So first simulations were done in the late 1940s by CHARNEY ET AL. (1950) [CFN50] and HANSEN (1956) [Han56] for oceanographic flows. In this context, the equations were used, for example, for predicting tidal movements, storm surges, and tsunamis. In meteorology, they help to model atmospheric phenomena such as cyclones and weather patterns. The first goal was a better understanding and more accurate predictions using numerical weather forecasting. Step by step, the models grew to include larger and more noticeable effects such as the Coriolis force. Through even greater precision, it was possible to reduce the size of the areas to be examined and make accurate

predictions for certain weather phenomena. So in the 1990s, it was possible to trace particle tracks, which is an important part of their dispersion. For the first time, it was possible to make predictions, for example, of Storm surges, for regions with few observations that are difficult to access. Civil engineers use SWE to design flood control systems and manage water resources. Interestingly, the principles of SWE are also applied in traffic flow analysis and crowd dynamics, where the movement of vehicles or people can be modelled similarly to fluid flow. The term *shallow water* is thus misleading, as it contains a range of phenomena beyond just water bodies, including atmospheric and even traffic systems.

To derive the shallow water equations, we need three steps:

- First, we combine the physical laws of conservation of mass and conservation of momentum with the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations.
- Second, we appropriate the free-surface and define boundary conditions for the Navier-Stokes equations.
- Third, we use hydrostatic pressure and the given boundary conditions to integrate the Navier-Stokes equations over depth.

1.1 Derivation of the Incompressible Navier-Stokes Equations

The Navier-Stokes Equations represent, in the case of an isothermal flow or a flow at constant temperature, two physical conservation laws: the conservation of mass and the conservation of momentum. We use the classical approach of continuum mechanics to derive these equations and follow along DAWSON AND MIRABITO [DM08], first seen in MCLAIN [McL22].

The Conservation of Mass

We can interpret the continuity equation for mass in the following way: For a given closed surface in our system, the change, over any time interval, of the mass enclosed by the surface is equal to the flux of the mass across the boundary. It's the so-called law of conservation of mass. We consider an arbitrary volume $V \subseteq \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ and write this as

$$\underbrace{\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho(x, t) d\mathbf{x}}_{\text{time rate of change of total mass in } V} = - \underbrace{\int_{\partial V} \rho \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{s}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{s}) d\mathbf{s}}_{\text{mass flux across the boundary of } V},$$

where ρ is the fluid density in $\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}\right]$, $\mathbf{v} = (v_1(x, t), v_2(x, t), v_3(x, t))$ the fluid velocity in $\left[\frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}\right]$ and \mathbf{n} the outward unit normal vector to the boundary ∂V . Applying

Gauss's Divergence Theorem gives us

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho(x, t) d\mathbf{x} = - \int_V \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v})(x, t) d\mathbf{x}.$$

We assume that ρ is smooth, so we can apply the Leibniz integral rule:

$$\int_V \left[\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}(x, t) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v})(x, t) \right] d\mathbf{x} = 0.$$

Now, we can combine all together and since V is chosen arbitrarily, we have

$$\left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) \right)(x, t) = 0. \quad (1.1.1)$$

We call 1.1.1 the continuity equation (CE), as the first of the two Navier-Stokes equations. For the second one, we follow a similar approach.

Remark 1.1.1 (Incompressible, homogeneous fluid). If the fluid is incompressible and homogeneous, i.e. composed of only one fluid, then $\rho(x, t) = \rho_0 > 0$ and 1.1.1 reduces to

$$(\partial_x v_1 + \partial_x v_2 + \partial_x v_3)(x, t) = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}(x, t) = 0 \quad \forall t \in (0, T], x \in \Omega.$$

In this case, the conservation of mass for an incompressible, homogeneous fluid imposes the velocity to be divergence-free.

The Conservation of Momentum

The Newton law implies that the rate of change of the momentum, in an arbitrary volume V , is equal to the sum of the flux of the momentum across the boundary ∂V , the body forces acting on the volume V , and the contact forces acting on the boundary ∂V . We can write this out as the following equation

$$\underbrace{\frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho \mathbf{v} d\mathbf{x}}_{\text{time rate of change of total momentum in } V} = - \underbrace{\int_{\partial V} (\rho \mathbf{v}) \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} ds}_{\text{momentum flux across boundary of } V} + \underbrace{\int_V \rho \mathbf{b} d\mathbf{x}}_{\text{body forces acting on } V} + \underbrace{\int_{\partial V} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{n} ds}_{\text{external contact forces acting on } \partial V},$$

where \mathbf{b} is the body force density per unit mass acting on the fluid in (N/kg) and \mathbf{T} is the Cauchy stress tensor in (N/m²).

As with the transport equation, the divergence theorem can be applied to the first and third terms on the right-hand side, which gives us

$$\int_V \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \mathbf{v}) d\mathbf{x} = - \int_V \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) d\mathbf{x} + \int_V \rho \mathbf{b} d\mathbf{x} - \int_V \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} d\mathbf{x} = 0.$$

We assume $\rho \mathbf{v}$ is smooth and use the Leibniz integral rule again:

$$\int_V \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) - \rho \mathbf{b} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} \right] d\mathbf{x} = 0.$$

Since V is an arbitrary volume,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) - \rho \mathbf{b} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} \right)(x, t) = 0. \quad (1.1.2)$$

So we have the second of the Navier-Stokes equations, the so-called momentum equation (ME).

Conservation Laws in Differential Form

Combining the differential forms of the equations for conservation and of mass and linear momentum, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) &= \rho \mathbf{b} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.1.3)$$

At this point, to obtain the Navier-Stokes equations, we need to make some assumptions about our fluid (i.e. saline water), about the density ρ and body forces \mathbf{b} and stress tensor \mathbf{T} .

Remark 1.1.2. Properties and Assumptions

- The fluid is incompressible, so the density ρ doesn't depend on pressure p . However, that doesn't mean ρ is constant — other factors like salinity and temperature can still affect it.
- In this work, in our domain, we assume salinity and temperature as constant, so we can consider ρ to be constant.

Therefore, we can reduce our continuity equation 1.1.1 to the divergence-free constraint on the velocity:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$$

- Hence, seawater is a Newtonian fluid; consequently, the form of \mathbf{T} would be affected, i.e. diagonal.

Body and Contact Forces

Body forces are external forces that act on the entire fluid uniformly. We can rewrite the body force term in the momentum equation 1.1.2 as

$$\rho \mathbf{b} = \rho(\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{rest}}), \quad (1.1.4)$$

here \mathbf{g} represents the acceleration due to gravity in $[\text{m/s}^2]$ and \mathbf{b}_{rest} includes all other body forces. The Coriolis force \mathbf{F}_C in $[\text{m/s}^2]$ will be the only body force besides gravity that we take into consideration.

Remark 1.1.3 (Coriolis Force). The Coriolis force is an inertial force, also named *pseudo-force* [Etl08]. If the ordinary Newtonian laws of motion of bodies are to be used in a rotating frame of reference, an inertial force must be included in the equations of motion. There are two different effects. On the one hand, an object that is moving in the same direction in absolute space will appear to change direction as the Earth rotates. On the other hand, an object on the Earth's surface carries the velocity of the Earth's rotation with it. Each effect causes an acceleration of the magnitude $\omega \sin(\theta v)$, where ω is the Earth's rate of rotation and θ is the geographic latitude. Combined we get the total acceleration of $2\omega \sin(\theta v)$ or $f\mathbf{v}$ with the Coriolis parameter $f = 2\omega \sin(\theta) = \frac{2\omega z}{R}$, R is defined as the radius of the sphere.

The Coriolis force acts tangential to the movement of the object, which leads to the following formulation in the Navier-Stokes equations

$$\mathbf{F}_C = f\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{v},$$

here $\mathbf{k} = (0, 0, 1)^T$ is the normal vector in the vertical direction.

We can write the contact forces for a Newtonian fluid in the following form

$$\mathbf{T} = -p\mathbb{I} + \overline{\mathbf{T}}, \quad (1.1.5)$$

where p is the fluid pressure in $[\frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2}]$, \mathbb{I} is the identity matrix and $\overline{\mathbf{T}}$ is a matrix of stress term, consisting of nine components and representing the state of stress at a given point,

$$\overline{\mathbf{T}} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau_{xx} & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \tau_{yy} & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \tau_{zz} \end{pmatrix}.$$

In this work, τ_{ij} is considered to represent the viscous stress at a given point and be expressed as

$$\tau_{ij} = \rho\nu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right), \quad (1.1.6)$$

Notation 1.1.4. To simplify the notation, x_j stands for (x, y, z) in the coordinate system and u_j for (u, v, w) for the velocity vector \mathbf{v} , with $j = 1, 2, 3$.

Three-Dimensional Navier-Stokes Equations

We can now include all the assumptions in the momentum equation 1.1.2. This gives us the final form of the 3D incompressible Navier-Stokes equations

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0 \\ \partial_t(\rho\mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) - \rho\mathbf{g} + \rho f\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{v} + \nabla p - \nabla \cdot \overline{\mathbf{T}} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.1.7)$$

with the gravitational vector $\mathbf{g} = (0, 0, -g)^T$ and the gravitational constant defined as $g \approx 9.81 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2}$.

1.2 Derivation of the Shallow Water Equations

We can now derive the shallow water equations from the Navier-Stokes equations by depth integration. We closely follow along [DM08] and [Vre94].

Surface and bottom boundary conditions

Firstly, it's necessary to establish boundary conditions on the domain. We can classify the surface and bottom boundary conditions into two categories, kinematic and dynamic. In general, dynamics describes the physical laws that determine the motion and kinematics the motion of particles. We will discuss the boundary conditions at the surface and bottom.

For better understanding and clarification of variables, we use the following sketch.

Figure 1.1: Shallow Water Equation, definition of variables

The kinematic conditions say that water particles won't cross either boundary. For the solid bottom, this means that the normal velocity component must vanish. In other words, when considering a normal vector to the bottom $\left(\frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial y}, -1\right)^T$, the velocity vector must be orthogonal, i.e. the two vectors have cross product of zero. This gives us

$$u \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial y} - w = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad z = z_b, \quad (1.2.1)$$

where z_b is the bottom level, measured from the horizontal reference level. It's more complicated for the free surface because it's moving by itself. The relative normal velocity gets an additional term compensating for the change in surface over time

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} - w = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad z = h. \quad (1.2.2)$$

Hereby, h is the surface level measured from a horizontal reference level. Secondly, we have dynamic boundary conditions, which say something about the forces acting at the boundaries. At the bottom, we have the so-called "no-slip" condition, which implies $u = v = 0$, i.e. there is no velocity in x - and y -directions. Furthermore, tangential stress components (τ_{bx}, τ_{by}) act at the bottom boundary of the water surface due to friction

$$\tau_{sx} = -\tau_{xx} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} - \tau_{xy} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} + \tau_{xz} \quad \text{at } z = h, \quad (1.2.3)$$

Similarly, for the y -direction. The wind stress vector on the left-hand side is supposed to be known as an external force (exists in x - and y -directions). At the free surface, a continuity of pressure is assumed, i.e. the pressure of the fluid near the surface is the same as the atmospheric pressure. So we find $p = p_a$, where p_a is the atmospheric pressure.

Hydrostatic Approximation

There is another central property, the so-called hydrostatic pressure distribution. We assume that the pressure is hydrostatic, which means that, if the fluid is continuous, the fluid pressure is assumed to have a linear distribution over the water column. This assumption allows us to simplify the vertical momentum equation. It can be written as the state equation for pressure

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = -\rho g.$$

We integrate the state equation over the depth of the water body, assume that the density ρ is constant over depth and get the equation for pressure

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\bar{z}}^h \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} dz &= \int_{\bar{z}}^h -\rho g dz, \\ p &= p_a + g \int_{\bar{z}}^h \rho dz \\ p &= p_a + \rho g(h - z). \end{aligned}$$

Here \bar{z} represents an arbitrary depth and we substitute the dynamic surface boundary conditions $p = p_a$ at $z = h$. With this, we can calculate the pressure gradients in the momentum equations. For example, the pressure gradient in x -direction:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial(p_a + g\rho(h - z))}{\partial x}.$$

After using the product rule and linearity, we receive the following identity, which we can substitute back into the equations:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial p_a}{\partial x} + g\rho \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}.$$

In the same way, we can calculate the y -direction. Bringing everything together and dividing both sides by the density ρ , this yields the momentum equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(u^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(uw) - fv + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p_a}{\partial x} + g \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} \right] &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(uv) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}(vw) + fu + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p_a}{\partial y} + g \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} - \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial z} \right] &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

Depth Integration

There is one final step towards the shallow water equations missing. It's the integration of the continuity equations and horizontal momentum equations over the depth $a = h - z_b$. This allows us to neglect the vertical velocity component from the equations.

Continuity Equation We integrate over the depth

$$0 = \int_{z_b}^h \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} dz,$$

and simplify after evaluating the term containing z to

$$0 = \int_{z_b}^h \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) dz + [w]_{z_b}^h.$$

Applying the Leibniz integral rule gives us

$$0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{z_b}^h u dz + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_{z_b}^h v dz - u|_{z=h} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + u|_{z=z_b} \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x} - v|_{z=h} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} + v|_{z=z_b} \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial y} + [w]_{z_b}^h.$$

Let the depth-averaged velocities \bar{u} and \bar{v} be defined as

$$\bar{u} = \frac{1}{a} \int_{z_b}^h u dz \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{v} = \frac{1}{a} \int_{z_b}^h v dz.$$

Finally, we can bring all together and the kinematic boundary conditions allow us to simplify the terms. The bottom terms cancel and the surface terms yield the rate of change of the surface level. So, we get the so-called depth-averaged continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(a\bar{u}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(a\bar{v}) = 0. \quad (1.2.4)$$

If we take a look at the mass balance for a vertical column of water, we can see it directly.

Momentum Equation Similar to the continuity equation, we integrate the left-hand side of the x -momentum equation 1.1.2 over depth and get:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{z_b}^h \left(\frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} \right) dz &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{z_b}^h \tau_{xx} dz + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_{z_b}^h \tau_{xy} dz \\ &- \left[\tau_{xx} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + \tau_{xy} \frac{\partial h}{\partial y} - \tau_{xz} \right]_{z=h} \\ &+ \left[\tau_{xx} \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial x} + \tau_{xy} \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial y} - \tau_{xz} \right]_{z=z_b}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.2.5)$$

and similar for the y -momentum equation. The advective term, the surface and the bottom terms cancel completely through the boundary conditions, but non-linear terms arise. The boundary integrals produce the bottom and surface shear stress components described before.

We get the following depth-averaged momentum equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(a\bar{u}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(a\bar{u}^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(a\bar{u}\bar{v}) - f\bar{a}\bar{v} + ga\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} &= \frac{1}{\rho}[\tau_{sx} - \tau_{bx} + F_x], \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(a\bar{v}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(a\bar{u}\bar{v}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(a\bar{v}^2) - f\bar{a}\bar{u} + ga\frac{\partial h}{\partial y} &= \frac{1}{\rho}[\tau_{sy} - \tau_{by} + F_y], \end{aligned} \quad (1.2.6)$$

where F_x and F_y are driving forces determined by the data of the problem. These include parameters such as wind stress, atmospheric pressure- and density gradients, radiation- and tidal stresses. More details can be found in Section 2.6 of [Vre94].

1.3 Shallow Water Equations

As written in [Vre94], we can now combine altogether and obtain the full system of the shallow water equations. We still assume that the velocity is depth-averaged,

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(au) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(av) = 0, \quad (1.3.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(au) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(au^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(auv) - fav + ga\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{\rho}[\tau_{sx} - \tau_{bx} + F_x], \quad (1.3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(av) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(auv) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(av^2) - f au + ga\frac{\partial h}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho}[\tau_{sy} - \tau_{by} + F_y]. \quad (1.3.3)$$

There are different forms of the SWE. We will examine two of these in more detail in the next section, using Chapter 2 of [Vre94].

Conservative and Nonconservative Momentum Equation

A distinction is made between conservative and non-conservative forms. The exact form of the momentum equation used is usually specified in the literature. The

conservative form of the momentum equation is obtained from 1.3.2 and 1.3.3 by disregarding lateral stresses and driving forces. For simplicity, we assume the bottom stresses, given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\tau_{bx}}{\rho} &= c_f u \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}, \\ \frac{\tau_{by}}{\rho} &= c_f v \sqrt{u^2 + v^2},\end{aligned}$$

where c_f is a friction coefficient. All together

$$\partial_t(av) + ((\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}) + f\mathbf{k} \times (a\mathbf{v}) + ag\nabla h + c_f\|\mathbf{v}\|\mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (1.3.4)$$

or, equivalently written out:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(au) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(au^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(auv) - fav + ga\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + c_f u \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} = 0, \quad (1.3.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(av) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(auv) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(av^2) - fau + ga\frac{\partial h}{\partial y} + c_f v \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} = 0. \quad (1.3.6)$$

If we now pair it with the continuity equation 1.1.7, we get the full system of the shallow water equations in conservative form. Let us now carry out the differentiation in the momentum equations 1.3.5 and 1.3.6 and simplify it with the continuity equation from 1.1.7, its so-called nonconservative form. While the conservative and nonconservative forms of the momentum equations are equivalent, this does not hold for the discretised forms, see [Vre94]. The nonconservative form of the equations can be derived as:

$$\partial_t \mathbf{v} + ((\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}) + f\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{v} + g\nabla h + \frac{c_f}{a}\|\mathbf{v}\|\mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (1.3.7)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} - fv + g\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + c_f\frac{u}{a}\sqrt{u^2 + v^2} = 0, \quad (1.3.8)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - fv + g\frac{\partial h}{\partial y} + c_f\frac{v}{a}\sqrt{u^2 + v^2} = 0. \quad (1.3.9)$$

Remark 1.3.1. For the full system of shallow water equations, we connect all with the continuity equation 1.1.7, its so-called nonconservative form. While the conservative and nonconservative form of the momentum equations are equivalent, this does not hold for the discretised forms, see [Vre94].

1.4 Linear and non-linear Shallow Water Equations

For our numerical approach, we simplify our model to a flat bottom topography. We further simplify the model by omitting the boundary terms. So the following illustration gives us an overview.

Figure 1.2: Shallow Water Equation with flat bottom

We are using the linearised shallow water equations in a rotating frame in 1-d form. The following equations model a single-layer fluid including the Coriolis term:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + f \mathbf{v}^\perp + g \nabla h &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \bar{h} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.1)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the horizontal velocity, h is the total fluid thickness, and depending on the simulation, \bar{h} is the constant reference layer depth. With f , we define the constant Coriolis Parameter (f-plane), and g is the acceleration due to gravity. Furthermore, [Rog+13] defines \mathbf{v}^\perp tangential to the sphere with $\mathbf{v}^\perp = \mathbf{n}_T \times \mathbf{v}$, with \mathbf{n}_T being the unit normal vector to the sphere for a cell T of the mesh. Since the problem is posed in a rotating frame set, the Coriolis Parameter can be written as $f = \frac{\Omega_0 z}{R}$. At this point, we want to introduce the non-linear shallow water equations. Therefore we can rewrite the momentum equation by $\zeta = \nabla^\perp \cdot \mathbf{u} = \text{div}(\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{n}_T)$, to

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\zeta + f) \mathbf{v}^\perp + \nabla \left(gh + \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{v}|^2 \right) = 0.$$

Now, we can define a potential vorticity $q = \frac{\zeta + f}{h}$, and obtain the non-linear SWE:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + q h \mathbf{v}^\perp + \nabla \left(gh + \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{v}|^2 \right) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h \mathbf{v}) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.2)$$

Remark 1.4.1. As written in [CM14], we name q as the shallow water potential vorticity. In a frictionless, adiabatic flow, the shallow water potential vorticity is conserved. This means that as a parcel of fluid moves around, its potential vorticity remains constant unless acted upon by external forces like friction or diabatic processes (e.g., heating or cooling). We have used

$$q = \frac{\nabla^\perp \cdot \mathbf{v} + f}{h}, \quad \nabla^\perp \cdot \mathbf{v} = -\frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x},$$

and the split $(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} = q\mathbf{v}^\perp + \nabla(\frac{|\mathbf{v}|^2}{2})$. If we now apply ∇^\perp to the momentum part of equation (1.4.2) and substitute the parts above, we obtain the conservation law for q :

$$\frac{\partial qh}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (qh\mathbf{v}) = 0. \quad (1.4.3)$$

This physical parameter takes an important role in predicting the large-scale balanced flow and explains Rossby Waves, which we will discuss later.

The flux form of the non-linear SWE with added advection terms, in 1-d, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial h\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) + f(h\mathbf{v})^\perp + gh\nabla(h + z_b) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v}) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.4)$$

where z_b is the parameter modelling the bottom topography (see 1.1). Our numerical research uses this non-linear form with $z_b = 0$ (flat bottom topography).

Remark 1.4.2 ((Non)Linear SWE (with Coriolis term)). Due to the large number of different terms, notations and designations for similar shallow-water equations, we would like to give a summarised overview again:

(i) Linearised SWE

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (f\mathbf{v}^\perp) + g\nabla h &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \bar{h}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.5)$$

(ii) Non-linear SWE

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (f\mathbf{v}^\perp) + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} + g\nabla h &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v}) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.6)$$

where $h\mathbf{v}$ is the non-linear mass flux and $(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v}$ the non-linear advection.

The fundamental difference is that the non-linear form also contains products of dynamic variables. This makes the solution somewhat more complex, but models the real flows and large disturbances very well. This makes the simulations more realistic for large amplitudes and/or discontinuities. The linear form is sufficient for small disturbances, acoustic approximations and wave analyses.

Different Forms of Non-linear SWE

The next few examples are all given with the Coriolis Force in the momentum equation.

Proposition 1.4.3 (Equivalent formulations of the non-linear SWE). *Suppose (v, h, q) is a smooth solution to (1.4.2), then it also solves the following equivalent formulations*

(i) *Conservative Form (used in CGDYCORE.JL)*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{v})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left(h\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{2}gh^2\mathbb{I} \right) + f\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (h\mathbf{v}) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.7)$$

(ii) *Flux Form, this form is identical to conservative, but more explicit.*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial h\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) + f(h\mathbf{v})^\perp + gh\nabla(h + z_b) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.8)$$

(iii) *Advective Form*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} + f\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\mathbf{v}) + g\nabla h &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla h + h\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.9)$$

(iv) *Vector-Invariant Form (used in CGDYCORE.JL)*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\zeta + f)\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v} + \nabla \left(\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{v}|^2 + gh \right) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v}) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.4.10)$$

where $\zeta = \nabla \times \mathbf{v} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} = \partial_x v_y - \partial_y v_x$ is the relative vorticity. The potential vorticity is defined as $q = \frac{\zeta + f}{h}$.

Proof. We show the equivalence of conservative and vector-invariant; the others are left to the reader.

(i) \iff (iv) :

We start with the Conservative Momentum Equation (with Coriolis Term),

$$\frac{\partial(h\mathbf{v})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left(h\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{2}gh^2\mathbb{I} \right) + f\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (h\mathbf{v}) = 0,$$

where we defined:

- \mathbf{v} : horizontal velocity, h : fluid depth, g : gravitational acceleration,
- f : Coriolis parameter (constant on (f-plane)), $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$: vertical unit vector and \mathbb{I} : identity matrix (for isotropic pressure)

In our second step, we expand all using the product rule and mass continuity. We apply the product rule to the time derivative and flux divergence and get

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial(h\mathbf{v})}{\partial t} &= h\frac{\partial\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}) &= h\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v}(\nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v})).\end{aligned}$$

Next, we substitute both into the momentum equation

$$h\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{v}\right) + \mathbf{v}\left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v})\right) + gh\nabla h + fh\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v} = 0.$$

Now, we use the mass continuity equation (conservative form of mass) $\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (h\mathbf{v}) = 0$ and set all together,

$$h\left(\frac{\partial\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{v} + f\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v} + g\nabla h\right) = 0. \quad (1.4.11)$$

In the third step, we apply the vector identity to the advective term. Therefore, we use:

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{v} = \nabla\left(\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{v}|^2\right) + (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) \times \mathbf{v}.$$

In 2D flows, the vorticity is given by $q = (\nabla \times \mathbf{v}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} = \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y}$, so we get

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\mathbf{v} = \nabla\left(\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{v}|^2\right) + q\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v}.$$

Now, we can substitute this into the previous expression:

$$\frac{\partial\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \zeta\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v} + f\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v} + \nabla\left(\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{v}|^2 + gh\right) = 0.$$

To conclude, we group the rotational terms and get the vector-invariant form of the shallow water momentum equation,

$$\frac{\partial\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\zeta + f)\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{v} + \nabla\left(\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{v}|^2 + gh\right) = 0. \quad (1.4.12)$$

It separates the time derivative, the rotational (vorticity + Coriolis) force, and the kinetic + potential energy gradient. \square

Remark 1.4.4. The bold symbols highlighted the vector quantities at the beginning of our discussion and should make it somewhat easier to understand the mathematical and physical quantities. We will now dispense with this notation.

We use in our code the conservative and vector-invariant form of the non-linear shallow-water equations.

Form	Description	Common Usage
Conservative Form	Written as divergence of fluxes; expresses conservation laws	Finite Element/Volume Methods, shock capturing
Flux Form	Specific version of conservative form with explicit flux terms	Numerical solvers (FVM, FDM)
Advective Form	Uses material derivatives like $v \cdot \nabla v$; non-conservative	Theoretical derivation, intuition
Vector-Invariant Form	Uses vorticity and energy gradient; highlights geophysical effects	Geophysical models (atmosphere, ocean)
Linearized Form	Approximates around equilibrium $h = H + \eta$, small disturbances	Wave analysis, analytic solutions

Table 1.1: Summary of common forms of the (Non)Shallow Water Equations (SWE)

Chapter 2

Finite Element Methods

In this section, we want to discuss the functional analytical basics of finite element methods. We investigate different spaces and results that will help solve the SWE. The theory is based on BRENNER [Bre10] and EVANS [Eva10], inspired by lecture notes of JUN.-PROF. MIRA SCHEDENSACK (LEIPZIG UNIVERSITY).

2.1 Functional analytical Basics

Definition 2.1.1. The space of smooth functions, infinitely often differentiable real functions with compact (closed and bounded) support in Ω ($\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ open, bounded), is denoted by $C_c^\infty(\Omega)$,

$$\begin{aligned} C_c^\infty(\Omega) &= \{v : v \in C^\infty(\Omega), \text{supp}(v) \subseteq \Omega\} \\ \text{supp}(v) &= \{x \in \Omega : v(x) \neq 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.1.2. In particular, functions from $C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ vanish in the neighbourhood of the boundary.

The space of the locally integrable functions $L^1_{\text{loc}}(\Omega)$ is defined by

$$L^1_{\text{loc}}(\Omega) := \{u : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable} : u \in L^1(K) \quad \forall K \subseteq \Omega \text{ compact}\}.$$

Definition 2.1.3 (Weak Derivative). Let $f, F \in L^1_{\text{loc}}(\Omega)$. If for all functions $g \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ it holds that

$$\int_{\Omega} F(x)g(x) \, dx = (-1)^{|\alpha|} \int_{\Omega} f(x)D^\alpha g(x) \, dx.$$

F is called the α -th weak derivative of f .

Definition 2.1.4 (Sobolev Spaces). Let $k \in \mathbb{N}_0, p \in [1, \infty]$. The Sobolev Space $W^{k,p}(\Omega)$ is defined by

$$W^{k,p}(\Omega) := \{u \in L^p(\Omega) : D^\alpha u \in L^p(\Omega) \quad \forall \alpha : |\alpha| \leq k\}.$$

We have assumed that all weak partial derivatives $\partial^\alpha u$ exist for $|\alpha| \leq k$. The space is equipped with the norm

$$\|u\|_{W^{k,p}(\Omega)} := \left(\sum_{|\alpha| \leq k} \|\partial^\alpha u\|_{L^p(\Omega)}^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad \text{if } 1 \leq p < \infty,$$

$$\|u\|_{W^{k,\infty}(\Omega)} := \max_{|\alpha| \leq k} \|\partial^\alpha u\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \quad \text{if } p = \infty.$$

Theorem 2.1.5 (Sobolev's Embedding). *Let $1 \leq p < \infty$ and $1 \leq q \leq \bar{p}$, with*

$$\bar{p} := \begin{cases} \frac{dp}{(d-p)} & p < d \\ \text{any } q \in [1, \infty) & p = d \\ \infty & p > d. \end{cases}$$

For all $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$ it holds that $u \in L^q(\Omega)$ and exists a constant $c < \infty$ with

$$\|u\|_{L^q(\Omega)} \leq c \|u\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}.$$

In other words the embedding $W^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega)$ is continuous. If $k > \frac{d}{p}$, then for all $u \in W^{k,p}(\Omega)$, we have $u \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$, and

$$\|u\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \leq c \|u\|_{W^{k,p}(\Omega)},$$

that means the embedding $W^{k,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ is continuous.

Remark 2.1.6. In the context of the Sobolev embedding theorem, the statement $u \in C(\bar{\Omega})$ is to be understood in the sense that there exists a representative $\tilde{u} \in C(\bar{\Omega})$ such that $\tilde{u} = u$ almost everywhere in Ω . In other words, the function u can be modified on a set of measure zero in such a way that the modified function is continuous on $\bar{\Omega}$. More precisely, this means that the equivalence class of u in $W^{k,p}(\Omega)$ contains a representative that belongs to $C(\bar{\Omega})$.

Theorem 2.1.7 (Rellich-Kondrachov). *Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ be an open, bounded Lipschitz domain and let $1 \leq \bar{p} < \infty$ and $1 \leq q \leq \bar{p}$ with \bar{p} from above. Then the embedding $W^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^q(\Omega)$ is compact, that means that all bounded sequences in $W^{1,p}(\Omega)$ have a subsequence which converges already in $L^q(\Omega)$.*

Proof. A proof can be found in BARTELS [Bar16, p. 90]. □

2.2 Ritz- and Galerkin Method

Finite Element Methods in the classical sense are special Galerkin methods. That's why we are discussing them more precisely in the next chapter. In this part, we say V is a Hilbert space with scalar product $(\cdot, \cdot)_V$. So V is \mathbb{R} - or \mathbb{C} -vector space and V is complete with respect to the induced norm $\|\cdot\|_V := \sqrt{(\cdot, \cdot)_V}$. We denote the

dual space of V , that is, the space of all linear and continuous maps $F : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, by V' . Equivalently, there exists c , such that

$$|F(v)| \leq c\|v\|_V \quad \forall v \in V.$$

Given a bilinearform $a : V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $F \in V'$ and want to find $u \in V$, such that

$$a(u, v) = F(v) \quad \forall v \in V. \quad (2.2.1)$$

Theorem 2.2.1 (Lax-Milgram). *Let V be a Hilbert space. If there is a bilinear form, which is*

i) coercive, that means there exists $\alpha > 0$ with

$$a(u, u) \geq \alpha\|u\|_V^2 \quad \forall u \in V,$$

ii) continuous, that means there exists $C < \infty$ with

$$|a(u, v)| \leq C\|u\|_V\|v\|_V \quad \forall u, v \in V.$$

For all $F \in V'$ there exists a unique solution $u \in V$ of (2.2.1) and it follows that

$$\|u\|_V \leq \frac{1}{\alpha}\|F\|_{V'}.$$

Proof. You can find the full proof in chapter 2 of BRENNER [Bre10, p. 70ff]. \square

Definition 2.2.2 (Galerkin approximation). We call $u_h \in V_h$ Galerkin approximation with closed subspace $V_h \subseteq V$, if

$$a(u_h, v_h) = F(v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (2.2.2)$$

Lemma 2.2.3 (Céa's Lemma). *We suppose that the conditions from above hold and $u_h \in V$ solves 2.2.2. That means there exists a unique Galerkin approximation and the Galerkin orthogonality*

$$a(u - u_h, v) = 0 \quad \forall v \in V_h$$

applies. For the finite element variational problem, we have

$$\|u - u_h\| \leq \frac{C}{\alpha} \inf_{v \in V_h} \|u - v\|_V, \quad (2.2.3)$$

where C is the continuity constant and α is the coercitivity constant of $a(\cdot, \cdot)$ on V .

Proof. For all $v \in V_h$,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha\|u - u_h\|_V^2 &\leq a(u - u_h, u - u_h) && \text{(by coercivity)} \\ &= a(u - u_h, u - v) + a(u - u_h, v - u_h) \\ &= a(u - u_h, u - u_h) && \text{(since } v - u_h \in V_h) \\ &\leq C\|u - u_h\|_V\|u - v\|_V. && \text{(by continuity)} \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|u - u_h\|_V \leq \frac{C}{\alpha} \|u - v\|_V \quad \forall v \in V_h.$$

Since V_h is closed,

$$\|u - u_h\|_V \leq \frac{C}{\alpha} \inf_{v \in V_h} \|u - v\|_V = \frac{C}{\alpha} \min_{v \in V_h} \|u - v\|_V. \quad \square$$

Remark 2.2.4. Céas Lemma shows that u_h is *quasi-optimal* in the sense that the error $\|u - u_h\|_V$ is proportional to the best it can be using the subspace V_h .

Definition 2.2.5 (Stiffness-matrix). A matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, which is defined by $A_{jk} := a(\phi_j, \phi_k) \quad \forall 1 \leq j, k \leq n$, is called stiffness matrix.

We define a vector $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ by $b_j := F(\phi_j)$. (Galerkin Approximation)

Proposition 2.2.6. *The Stiffness matrix A is positive definite and for the unique solution $U \in \mathbb{R}^n$ of $A^T U = b$ we have*

$$u_h = \sum_{j=1}^n U_j \phi_j.$$

Proof. For $W \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we define $w_h := \sum_{j=1}^n W_j \phi_j$. So

$$\begin{aligned} W^T A W &= \sum_{j,k=1}^n W_j A_{jk} W_k = \sum_{j,k=1}^n W_j a(\phi_j, \phi_k) W_k \\ &= \sum_{j,k=1}^n a(W_j \phi_j, W_k \phi_k) = a(w_h, w_h) \geq \alpha \|w_h\|_V^2. \end{aligned}$$

Because $w_h = 0$, iff. $W = 0$, A is positive definite and hence invertible. Now we have $w_h \in V_h$ and $W \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $w_h = \sum_{j=1}^n W_j \phi_j$. We thus get

$$\begin{aligned} a(u_h, w_h) &= \sum_{j,k=1}^n U_j a(\phi_j, \phi_k) W_k = (A^T U)^T W, \\ F(w_h) &= \sum_{j=1}^n W_j F(\phi_j) = \sum_{j=1}^n W_j b_j = b^T W, \end{aligned}$$

and so

$$a(u_h, w_h) = F(w_h) \iff A^T U = b. \quad \square$$

2.3 Finite Elements

General Mesh

Definition 2.3.1 (Mesh). Let M be a Lipschitz domain in \mathbb{R}^d . We say \mathcal{T}_h is mesh of M if \mathcal{T}_h is a finite collection of closed subsets of M , called mesh cells (or mesh elements), such

1. the interiors of mesh cells are all nonempty Lipschitz domains in \mathbb{R}^d , mutually disjoint,
2. $\bar{M} = \cup_{k \in \mathcal{T}_h} K$, all meshes cover \bar{M} exactly.

Definition 2.3.2 (Mesh size). The subscript h refers to a level refinement. There are multiple different (e.g., red refinement).

$$h := \max_{k \in \mathcal{T}_h} h_k \quad h_k := \text{diam}(K) := \max_{x_1, x_2 \in K} \|x_1 - x_2\|,$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm.

Remark 2.3.3. We notice that in general, mesh elements have a simple shape. But for simplicity, we assume that all the mesh cells have been generated from a fixed reference cell $\hat{K} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, so that there is a smooth diffeomorphism $T_K : \hat{K} \rightarrow K \quad \forall K \in \mathcal{T}_h$. It is not forbidden to mix different kinds of elements, like triangles and quadrangles, in one mesh. In our code, it's only possible to use one type per mesh.

Figure 2.1: Geometric Mapping from reference element \hat{K} (left) to three different cells in the mesh \mathcal{T}_h

Definition 2.3.4 (affine/non-affine). We say a mesh \mathcal{T}_h is simplicial when the reference element \hat{K} is a simplex. The mesh \mathcal{T}_h is said to be affine when all the geometric mappings $\{T_K\}_{K \in \mathcal{T}_h}$ are affine.

Definition 2.3.5 (Faces, Edges and vertices). Be $K \in \mathcal{T}_h$ a cell. We assume $d = 3$, the faces, edges and vertices of K are defined as images of T_k of the faces, edges and vertices of our reference polyhedron \hat{K} . We define the collections of these sets as $\mathcal{F}_K, \mathcal{E}_K$ and \mathcal{V}_K . These definitions exactly hold for $d = 2$, besides edges and faces coincide.

Definition 2.3.6 (Mesh faces, edges and vertices). Let \mathcal{T}_h be a mesh. We assume $d = 3$. A closed two-dimensional manifold $F \subset \bar{M}$ is a mesh face if there is a mesh cell $K \in \mathcal{T}_h$ s.t. F is a face of K , i.e., $F \in \mathcal{F}_K$. Similarly, a closed one-dimensional manifold $E \subset \bar{M}$ is a mesh edge if there is a mesh cell $K \in \mathcal{T}_h$, s.t. $E \in \mathcal{E}_K$. Moreover, a point $z \in \bar{M}$ is a mesh vertex if there is a mesh cell $K \in \mathcal{T}_h$ s.t. $z \in \mathcal{V}_K$.

Elements and Shape functions

Definition 2.3.7 (Finite element). Let $d \geq 1, \hat{n} \geq 1, \hat{n} \in \mathbb{N}, \mathcal{N} := \{1, \dots, \hat{n}\}$, then a tripl (K, P, Σ) is called finite element, with

- (i) K is a polyhedron in \mathbb{R}^d , more generally, K could be the closure of a connected and non-empty Lipschitz domain in \mathbb{R}^d .
- (ii) P is a finite-dimensional vector space of functions $p : K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q, q \geq 1, q \in \{1, \dots, d\}$. Moreover, members of P are polynomial functions composed of some smooth diffeomorphism.
- (iii) Σ is a set of n linear forms from P to \mathbb{R} and we can say, that $\Sigma := \{\sigma_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ and $\Phi_\Sigma : P \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\hat{n}}, \Phi_\Sigma(p) := (\sigma_i(p))_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ is an isomorphism. We call σ_i degrees of freedom, short form dofs.

Remark 2.3.8. The bijectivity of Φ_Σ is referred to as unisolvence. It's equivalent to $\Phi_\Sigma : P \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\hat{n}} \quad \forall (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n \quad \exists! p \in P : \sigma_i(p) = \alpha_i \quad \forall 1 \leq i \leq n$. So we can say:

$$\begin{cases} \dim P = |\Sigma| = n \\ \forall p \in P : \sigma_i(p) = 0 \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n \Rightarrow p = 0. \end{cases}$$

Proposition 2.3.9. *Shape functions*

- (i) *There is a basis $\{\Theta_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ of P s.t.*

$$\sigma_i(\Theta_j) := \delta_{ij}, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}.$$

The functions Θ_i are called shape functions.

- (ii) *Let $\{\phi_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ be basis of P . If we are defining the generalized Vandermonde matrix as $\mathcal{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{n} \times \hat{n}}$ with entries $\mathcal{V}_{ij} := \sigma_j(\phi_i) \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}$, the shape functions are given by*

$$\Theta_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (\mathcal{V}^{-1})_{ij} \phi_j, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}.$$

Proof. (i) The shape functions are given by $\Theta_i = \Phi_\Sigma^{-1}(e_i) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$, where $(e_i)_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ is the canonical basis of $\mathbb{R}^{\hat{n}}$.

- (ii) We want to show that the matrix \mathcal{V} is invertible. Therefore, we consider $X \in \mathbb{R}^{\hat{n}}$ such that $X^\top \mathcal{V} = 0$ and $p := \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} X_i \phi_i$. So $X^\top \mathcal{V} = 0$ implies that $\sigma_j(p) = 0 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}$. Together with 2.3.8 we get, that $p = 0$. Because $\{\phi_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ is a basis of $P, X = 0$. Finally, $\sigma_k \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (\mathcal{V}^{-1})_{ij} \phi_j \right) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (\mathcal{V}^{-1})_{ij} \sigma_k(\phi_j) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (\mathcal{V}^{-1})_{ij} \mathcal{V}_{jk} = \delta_{ik} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{N}$. This proves that $\Theta_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (\mathcal{V}^{-1})_{ij} \phi_j, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$. \square

Remark 2.3.10. The Proposition 2.3.9 above gives us a recipe to build the shape functions. First choose the basis of P , second evaluate the associated Vandermonde Matrix \mathcal{V} and its inverse and with that the shape functions Θ_i in the chosen basis are then $\mathcal{V}_{ij}^{-1}\phi_j$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{N}$.

Remark 2.3.11. For $d = 1$, we define the classical *Vandermonde matrix* with entries $\mathcal{V}_{ij} = a_j^i \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}$, if we are using the monomial basis $\{x^i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ with the dofs $\sigma_i(p) := p(a_i)$.

The interpolation operator plays a central part in the finite-element theory. It is used in a broad sense, since the degrees of freedom are not always point evaluations. The interpolation operator works on an extended domain of the linear forms in Σ , so they can act on functions in a space larger than P . We call the space $V(K)$ the fourth ingredient defining a finite element.

Definition 2.3.12 (Interpolation operator). Let (K, P, Σ) be a finite element. Assume that there exists a Banach space $V(K) \subseteq L^1(K, \mathbb{R}^q)$ with L^1 norm s.t.:

- (i) $P \subseteq V(K)$
- (ii) We can extend the linear forms $\{\sigma_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ to $\mathcal{L}(V(K), \mathbb{R})$, i.e. there exists $\{\tilde{\sigma}_i\}_i \in \mathcal{N}$ and c_Σ s.t. $\tilde{\sigma}_i(p) \quad \forall p \in P$ and $|\tilde{\sigma}_i(v)| \leq c_\Sigma \|v\|_{V(K)} \quad \forall v \in V(K), \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$. For simplicity, we change the notation and use the symbol σ_i instead of $\tilde{\sigma}_i$.

We define the interpolation operator $\mathcal{I}_K : V(K) \rightarrow P$ as

$$\mathcal{I}_K(v)(\mathbf{x}) := \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sigma_i(v) \Theta_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in K, \forall v \in V(K). \quad (2.3.1)$$

We denote $V(K)$ as the domain of \mathcal{I}_K and P as the codomain.

Remark 2.3.13 (Boundedness). \mathcal{I}_K belongs to $\mathcal{L}(V(K); P)$.

Proof. Let $\|\cdot\|_P$ be a norm in the finite-dimensional space P . Together with the triangle inequality and Definition 2.3.12, we can conclude the proof:

$$\|\mathcal{I}_K(v)\|_P \leq \left(c_\Sigma \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \|\Theta_i\|_P \right) \|v\|_{V(K)} \quad \forall v \in V(K). \quad \square$$

Remark 2.3.14 (P -invariance). P is pointwise invariant under \mathcal{I}_K , i.e. $\mathcal{I}_K(p) = p \quad \forall p \in P$. As a consequence, \mathcal{I}_K is a projection, i.e. $\mathcal{I}_K \circ \mathcal{I}_K = \mathcal{I}_K$.

Proof. Applying \mathcal{I}_K to $p = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_j \Theta_j$ yields $\mathcal{I}_K(p) = \sum_{i, j \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_j \sigma_i(\Theta_j) (\Theta_i) = p$ owing to 2.3.9. So this shows us that P is pointwise invariant under \mathcal{I}_K and immediately follows that \mathcal{I}_K is a projection. \square

At this point, we want to introduce the first and very standard Lagrange finite element.

Definition 2.3.15 (Lagrange Finite Element). Let (K, P, Σ) be a scalar-valued finite element. If we have a set of points $\{\alpha_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ in K such that $\forall i \in \mathcal{N}$,

$$\sigma_i(p) := p(a_i) \quad \forall p \in P,$$

the triple (K, P, Σ) is called Lagrange finite element. The points $\{\alpha_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ are called *nodes* and the shape functions $\{\Theta_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$, which are defined as

$$\Theta_i(a_j) := \delta_{ij}, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N},$$

form the nodal basis of P . They are associated with the nodes $\{a_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$. We can define the *Lagrange interpolation operator* \mathcal{I}_K^L as

$$\mathcal{I}_K^L(v)(x) := \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} v(a_i) \Theta_i(x), \quad \forall x \in K.$$

Proposition 2.3.16 (Finite element generation). Let $(\hat{K}, \hat{P}, \hat{\Sigma})$ be the reference element with extended dofs $\{\hat{\sigma}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{V}(\hat{K}); \mathbb{R})$ and $K \in \mathcal{T}_h$ be a mesh cell. We assume that we have a Banach space $V(K)$ and a bounded linear isomorphism $\psi_K \in \mathcal{L}(V(K); V(\hat{K}))$. So the triple (K, P_K, Σ_K) , defined by

$$P_K := \psi_K^{-1}(\hat{P}) = \{p := \psi_K^{-1}(\hat{p}) \mid \hat{p} \in \hat{P}\} \quad (2.3.2)$$

$$\Sigma_K := \hat{\Sigma} \circ \psi_K = \{\sigma_{K,i} := \hat{\sigma}_i \circ \psi_K\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{L}(P_K; \mathbb{R}), \quad (2.3.3)$$

is a finite element. We can extend the dofs in Σ_K to $\mathcal{L}(V(K); \mathbb{R})$ by setting $\sigma_{K,i} := \hat{\sigma}_i \circ \psi_K \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$.

Proof. We want to prove that (K, P_K, Σ_K) is a finite element. Due to the bijectivity of ψ_K , $\dim(P) = \dim(\hat{P})$. We let $p \in P_K$ be s.t. $\sigma_{K,i}(p) = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$. Then $\hat{\sigma}_i(\psi_K(p)) = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$, so because of the unisolvence property of $(\hat{K}, \hat{P}, \hat{\Sigma})$, we have $\psi_K(p) = 0$. Since ψ_K is an isomorphism, this implies that $p = 0$. Moreover, since $(\hat{\sigma}_i \circ \psi_K)|_P = \hat{\sigma}_i \circ \psi_K$, the linear map $\hat{\sigma}_i \circ \psi_K : V_K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an extension of $\sigma_{K,i} : P_K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ to $V(K)$. So all in all, we have $\sigma_{K,i} \in \mathcal{L}(V(K); \mathbb{R})$ since $|\sigma_{K,i}(v)| \leq \|\hat{\sigma}_i\|_{\mathcal{L}(V(\hat{K}); \mathbb{R})} \|\psi_K\|_{\mathcal{L}(V(K); V(\hat{K}))} \quad \forall v \in V(K)$. \square

Remark 2.3.17. Finally, we can give new names to some mathematical formulations. So the linear forms $\{\sigma_{K,i}\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ are called *local dofs*.

Besides, we call $\Theta_{K,i} := \Psi_K^{-1}(\hat{\Theta}_i) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$, *local shape functions*, satisfying, $\sigma_{K,i} = \hat{\sigma}_i(\Theta_{K,j}) = \hat{\sigma}_i(\Psi_K(\Theta_{K,j})) = \hat{\sigma}_i(\hat{\Theta}_j) = \delta_{ij} \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}$. The *local interpolation operator* $\mathcal{I}_K : V(K) \rightarrow P_K$ from above, can be written explicitly as

$$\mathcal{I}_K(v)(x) := \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sigma_{K,i}(v) \Theta_{K,i}(x), \quad \forall x \in K.$$

These results play a key role in the finite element analysis later on. The last section was closely based on the book [EG21].

Chapter 3

Finite Elements on the Sphere

Our main goal is to numerically solve the equations on the sphere, i.e., the nonlinear shallow water equations. For this, we have implemented finite element methods in Julia. In the first step, the idea is to project the sphere as a manifold onto the reference element. Next, we want to solve the equations on the reference element and bring it back afterwards to the Triangular or Cubed Sphere. Besides the mesh construction and coordinate transformation, we take a look at the main technical points of transformations in the next chapter. Moreover, the different kinds of finite elements play an important role.

3.1 Spherical Grid Construction

Cubed Sphere

Firstly, we discuss the main idea behind a Cubed Sphere. It's a new gridding technique based on a decomposition of the sphere into six identical regions. The main idea of RONCHI [RIP96] is to project the sides of a circumscribed cube onto a spherical surface. So we get six nonconformal mappings, which are free of any singularity, define the same metric and allow the construction of a quasi-uniform physical grid. The construction is based on one main point. The six meshes are built from two sets of angularly equidistant great circles, where each of the arcs of the great circles can be associated with either a vertical or horizontal coordinate line. So we want to achieve regions of identical size. The methodology presented in [RIP96] rests on several fundamental criteria. The mapping utilised must be devoid of singularities to guarantee smoothness and numerical robustness. It is essential that the mapping preserves the intrinsic form of the hydrodynamic equations, thereby maintaining their physical consistency. Moreover, the computational grid constructed on the spherical surface should closely approximate a uniform, equidistant mesh, with the equator aligned as a coordinate line of the grid network. Lastly, the numerical scheme developed must demonstrate competitiveness with spectral transform methods in both accuracy and computational performance. Later in our research, we will see some regions that are prone to numerical instability. On

the one hand, they are the corners of the former cube. We saw this in the test cases, e.g., by Galewsky, the numerical accuracy often fails to remain in the expected bounds.

Figure 3.1: Stepwise transformation from a cube to a cubed sphere based on projection techniques developed by RONCHI et al. [RIP96], providing a uniform spherical grid for numerical analysis.

Triangular Sphere

Basic considerations and properties of the Triangular Sphere are the same as those of the Cubed Sphere. However, they differ in a few ways. In our consideration, we are using the work of TOMITA [Tom+01]. In Figure 3.2 we see a schema of the Triangular Grid Construction. The points denoted by black circles are the vertices of triangular grid elements, these are variable-defined points. The points denoted by black triangles are the gravitational centres of triangular grid elements. The point P_0 is the middle point of its control volume, which is the polygon constructed by connecting the gravitational centres of neighbouring triangular grid elements. The control volumes are generally hexagonal, except for several that are pentagonal. This means that a Triangular Sphere has a pentagon at each of the bonding surfaces of the individual hexagons (see 3.3). Note that it is at only 12 points inherited from the original icosahedron.

Construction 3.1.1 (Grid Construction Process).

1. **Initial Icosahedron:** Start with a regular icosahedron inscribed in a sphere. An icosahedron has 20 triangular faces, 12 vertices, and 30 edges.
2. **Subdivision:** Each triangular face of the icosahedron is subdivided into smaller triangles. This process can be repeated multiple times, creating a finer grid with more triangular faces at each level of subdivision. For each subdivision, new vertices are created along the edges of the original triangles, and these vertices are projected onto the sphere's surface to maintain the spherical shape.
3. **Refinement:** There are different ways to refine the grid. One variant is the subdividing of each triangular face into four smaller triangles by connecting the midpoints of the edges. This results in a hierarchy of tessellations derived

Figure 3.2: Schematic figure of Triangular Grid Construction

Figure 3.3: Triangular Grid on the Sphere

Figure 3.4: Construction of the Triangular Grid on the Sphere

from successive dyadic refinements of the spherical icosahedron. Another one is to divide every triangle into 3 other triangles by using the midpoint of each main triangle. (see 3.2)

4. **Grid-Point Placement:** Grid points are placed at the vertices of the subdivided triangles. These grid points are then used to perform calculations in Cartesian coordinates within local neighbourhoods of the icosahedral grid.

Remark 3.1.2 (Advantages of the Method:). The resulting grid is more uniform/regular compared to traditional latitude-longitude grids, especially near the poles, where other grids may become distorted. Furthermore, the method reduces computational complexity and improves efficiency in numerical simulations. In addition to this, the grid can be easily refined to achieve higher resolutions as needed for different applications.

3.2 Galerkin Projection on the Manifold

The Galerkin projection involves projecting a high-dimensional system onto a lower-dimensional subspace (manifold) to simplify the problem while retaining essential dynamics. So we map each cell $T \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ with physical dimension n to a reference cell $\hat{T} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ with topological dimension m . We assume that such a mapping $G_T : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ with $T = G_T(\hat{T})$ exists for all cell T of the mesh $\mathcal{T} = \{T_n\}$ (see figure 3.5). Throughout the section, let Ω be a smooth m -dimensional manifold immersed in \mathbb{R}^n , with $m \leq n$. For our case in the spherical setting, we set $m = 2$ and $n = 3$. If we are using the Cubed Sphere as a kind of mesh, our reference

element is a square $\hat{T} = [-1, 1]^2$. The Triangular Grid has the reference triangle with the nodes in $\hat{T} = \{(-1, -1), (1, -1), (-1, 1)\}$.

Notation 3.2.1. We write here and throughout $X = (X_1, \dots, X_m)$ for the coordinates in reference space and $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ for points of the coordinates in physical space. 3.5 illustrates this mapping and our notation.

Figure 3.5: Transformation between reference triangle and physical space

Now, we want to define some important variables. But first, some more notation:

Notation 3.2.2. Denote by DG_T the Jacobian matrix of the coordinate mapping G_T and $\det(DG_T)$ its determinant. Note that we named in our general introduction the physical and reference element with K and \hat{K} . In our explicit application, we now switch to T respectively \hat{T} .

Proposition 3.2.3 (integral transformation). *Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ an open set and $\Phi : \Omega \rightarrow \Phi(\Omega) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ a diffeomorphism. Then the function f is integrable on $\Phi(\Omega)$ iff the function $x \mapsto f(\Phi(x)) \cdot |\det(D\Phi(x))|$ is integrable on Ω . In this case:*

$$\int_{\Phi(\Omega)} f(y) dy = \int_{\Omega} f(\Phi(x)) \cdot |\det(D\Phi(x))| dx. \quad (3.2.1)$$

In particular the integral of a cell $T \in \mathcal{T}$ transformed to our reference cell \hat{T} is given by

$$\int_T f(x) dx = \int_{\hat{T}} f(\Phi(X)) |\det DG_T| dX, \quad (3.2.2)$$

where $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and $X = (X_1, \dots, X_m)$ denote the point coordinates in the physical and the reference space.

Definition 3.2.4 (Jacobian and it's pseudodeterminant). The Jacobian \mathbf{J} of the transform $G : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is defined by the matrix:

$$(DG_T)_{ij} = \mathbf{J}_{i,j} = \frac{\partial G(X)_i}{\partial X_j} = \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial X_j} \quad (3.2.3)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, \dots, m$. Note that j varies over the dimension of the manifold m . It's also the geometric and topological dimension of the reference cell. Where i varies over the physical dimension n . In our spherical setting with $m = 2$ and $n = 3$ we get

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial X_1} & \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial X_2} \\ \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial X_1} & \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial X_2} \\ \frac{\partial x_3}{\partial X_1} & \frac{\partial x_3}{\partial X_2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Corollary 3.2.5. *The transformation of an edge $e \in \mathcal{E}$, of the mesh cell T to the corresponding edge E of the reference cell \hat{T} is given by*

$$\int_e dx = \int_E \dots |\det J_E| dX.$$

Here we have $J_E = \det(DG_T)_{ij} \|(DG_T^{-1})^\top \cdot \mathbf{n}_E\|$, where \mathbf{n}_E denotes the normal of E .

Proof. The proof can be found in [Rog+13]. □

Remark 3.2.6. In summary, we see the importance of the Jacobian matrix and its determinant, which later becomes even greater for the orientation of our elements. We consider the flux over an edge $e \in \mathcal{E}$, with \mathcal{E} the set of all edges in \mathcal{T} , it's the so-called edge Jacobian.

Remark 3.2.7. For our affine transformation G_T , the Jacobian J_{G_T} is constant over each cell. In the case of curved cells, with non-affine transformation, the Jacobian varies as a function of X .

When we have an immersed manifold $m < n$, the Jacobian matrix is no longer quadratic, see 3.2.4. So the critical point is to define the pseudo-determinant. Because of the non-quadratic shape, we have to use the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse. For more details, see ROGNES ET AL. [Rog+13].

3.3 Transformation of Nodal functions

Definition 3.3.1 (pullback). Let ϕ denote the scalar-valued basis function in the physical space. The pullback Φ of those functions to the reference cell is defined as

$$\Phi_i(X) = \phi_i(x) = \phi_i(G_T(X)).$$

With the definitions and results above, we get

$$\int_T \phi_i(x) \phi_j(x) dx = \int_T \phi_i(G_T(X)) \phi_j(G_T(X)) dx = \int_{\hat{T}} \Phi_i(X) \Phi_j(X) \det(DG_T) dX.$$

Notation 3.3.2 (Moore-Penrose Inverse). For a given matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, the Moore-Penrose inverse is denoted by A^\dagger . It is the unique matrix $A^\dagger \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ satisfying the

following four Penrose conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} AA^\dagger A &= A, \\ A^\dagger AA^\dagger &= A^\dagger, \\ (AA^\dagger)^\top &= AA^\dagger, \\ (A^\dagger A)^\top &= A^\dagger A. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.3.3 (Gradient). Moreover, we define the pullback of the gradient of a scalar-valued field to the reference element,

$$\nabla_x \phi(x) = (DF_T^\dagger)^\top \nabla_X \Phi(X).$$

The gradient of a vector-valued field can be written, by using the tensor product, as

$$\nabla_x \phi(x) = (\nabla \otimes \phi(x))^\top = \phi(x) \otimes \nabla = \phi(x) \nabla^\top.$$

For the gradient of div-conforming Raviart-Thomas elements to be expressed using gradient information from the reference space, the Jacobian would have to be differentiated again, see [VK22]. A simplification of the formula only exists if the Jacobian is constant. So it's given by

$$\nabla_x \phi(x) = \frac{1}{J_T} DF_T \nabla_X \Phi(X) DF_T^{-1}.$$

Besides the Cartesian product of scalar-valued component spaces, we also use div-conforming Raviart-Thomas elements. These are typically used for modelling ocean and atmospheric processes. So, instead of a simple pullback, we are using the contravariant Piola mapping.

Definition 3.3.4 (contravariant Piola mapping). We consider the affine function $G_T : \hat{T} \rightarrow T$. In general the Piola transform is defined as $P : L^2(\hat{T}) \rightarrow L^2(T)$

$$P(\hat{q})(x) := \frac{1}{|J_{G_T}|} J_{G_T} \hat{q}(x). \quad (3.3.1)$$

In our setting, the *contravariant Piola mapping* is defined as

$$P^n(\Phi(x)) = \frac{1}{|J_{G_T}|} DF_T \Phi(X) = \frac{1}{|J_{G_T}|} DF_T \Phi(F_T^{-1}(x)). \quad (3.3.2)$$

It conserves the continuity in normal direction. In addition, we can define the *covariant Piola mapping*, which preserves the tangential components,

$$P^t(\Phi(x)) = (DF_T \Phi(X))^T \Phi(F_T^{-1}(x)). \quad (3.3.3)$$

Integral Transformation

We use the descriptions of [VK22]. These transformations can be effortlessly converted into an integral through substitution, allowing for integration over a reference cell \hat{T} . Such integrals commonly appear as the product of two functions under certain operators. To maintain clarity and brevity, the operators $(\cdot, \cdot)_{\mathcal{T}}$ as well as $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{E}}$ are introduced,

Definition 3.3.5 (scalar-valued).

$$(\phi, \psi)_{\mathcal{T}} = \sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \int_T \phi \psi dx = \sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \int_{T_0} \Phi \Psi |J_{G_T}| dX, \quad (3.3.4)$$

$$\langle \phi, \psi \rangle_{\mathcal{T}} = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \int_e \phi \psi dx = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \int_E \Phi \Psi |J_e| dX. \quad (3.3.5)$$

For the scalar-valued component spaces, we have to work with the Cartesian product of the vectorial nodal functions ϕ and ψ . The operators are similar. Let ϕ and ϕ denote the scalar- and vector-valued basis functions in the physical space as well as Φ and Φ their respective pullback to the reference cell.

In the case of div-conforming Raviart-Thomas elements with the nodal functions ϕ and ψ , they are obtained by

Definition 3.3.6 (vector-valued with RT-Element space).

$$(\phi, \psi)_{\mathcal{T}} = \sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \int_T \phi \psi dx = \sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \int_{T_0} \frac{|J_e|}{J_{G_T}^2} DF_{G_T} \Phi \cdot DF_{G_T} \Psi dX, \quad (3.3.6)$$

$$\langle \phi, \psi \rangle_{\mathcal{T}} = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \int_e \phi \psi dx = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \int_E \frac{|J_e|}{J_{G_T}^2} DF_{G_T} \Phi \cdot DF_{G_T} \Psi dX. \quad (3.3.7)$$

Remark 3.3.7. Directly from the definitions we can see that $(\cdot, \cdot)_{\mathcal{T}}$ as well as $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathcal{E}}$ are symmetric.

Edges

Before proceeding with flux computation over an edge, additional formulas and notations must be introduced, see [LB13]. Let \mathcal{E}_I as the set of all interior edges of the mesh \mathcal{T} . Each edge $e \in \mathcal{E}_I$ is assigned a fixed unit normal \mathbf{n}_e . The transformation of the normal \mathbf{n}_e for a given edge e is then defined as follows:

$$n_e = \frac{1}{J_e} J_{G_T} (DF_T^{-1})^\top n_E,$$

where E is the corresponding edge of the reference element. The two cells, which are adjacent to an interior edge $e \in \mathcal{E}_I$ shall be distinguished based on the exterior normal. Here, T^+ is the face with n_e and T^- with $-n_e$ as the exterior normal.

Figure 3.6: Two adjacent cells T^- and T^+ connected by edge e and unit normal n_e .

Definition 3.3.8. We can define the jump and average of a discontinuous function f at the interior edge $e \in \mathcal{E}_I$ as

$$\begin{aligned} [[f]] &= f_+ - f_- \\ \langle\langle f \rangle\rangle &= \frac{1}{2}(f_+ + f_-), \end{aligned}$$

here f_+ and f_- denote the part of discontinuous, piecewise function f defined on T^+ and T^- , the to e adjacent cell, see [VK22] and [CW20].

3.4 Finite Elements

H(div) finite elements

Since we mainly use Raviart-Thomas elements in our work, we will focus on this type of H(Div) elements. In this part, we detail the construction following along [EG21].

The polynomial space $\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$

Definition 3.4.1 (multi-index set). The set $\mathcal{A}_{k,d} := \{\alpha \in \mathbb{N}^d \mid |\alpha| \leq k\}$ is called multi-index set, where $|\alpha| := \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_d$. In addition to this we want to introduce the subset $\mathcal{A}_{k,d}^H := \{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}_{k,d} \mid |\alpha| = k\}$.

Definition 3.4.2 (Homogeneous polynomials). We call a polynomial $p \in \mathbb{P}_{k,d}$ homogeneous of degree k if $p(x) = \sum_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}_{k,d}^H} a_\alpha x^\alpha$ with real coefficients a_α . The real vector space, which is composed of homogeneous polynomials, is denoted by $\mathbb{P}_{k,d}^H$ or \mathbb{P}_k^H , when the context is unambiguous.

Lemma 3.4.3 (Properties of $\mathbb{P}_{k,d}^H$). We have $x \cdot \nabla q = kq$, which is called Euler's identity and $\nabla \cdot (xq) = (k+d)q \quad \forall q \in \mathbb{P}_{k,d}^H$.

Proof. We can use the linearity and show that yields $q(x) := x^\alpha \quad \forall \alpha \in \mathcal{A}_{k,d}^H$. Writing all together we get,

$$x \cdot \nabla q = \sum_{i \in \{1:d\}} \alpha_i x_i x_1^{\alpha_1} \dots x_i^{\alpha_i - 1} \dots x_d^{\alpha_d} = \left(\sum_{i \in \{1:d\}} \alpha_i \right) q = kq.$$

Our second property follows from $\nabla \cdot x = d$ and $\nabla \cdot (xq) = q \nabla \cdot x + x \cdot \nabla q$. \square

Definition 3.4.4 ($\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$). Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $d \geq 2$. We define the following real vector space of \mathbb{R}^d -valued polynomials:

$$\mathbb{RT}_{k,d} := \mathbb{P}_{k,d} \otimes x\mathbb{P}_{k,d}^H. \quad (3.4.1)$$

Note that the above tensor product is direct since the polynomials in $x\mathbb{P}_{k,d}^H$ are members of $x\mathbb{P}_{k+1,d}^H$, while the degree of any polynomial in $\mathbb{P}_{k,d}$ doesn't exceed k .

Example 3.4.5. ($k = 1, d = 2$) $\dim(\mathbb{RT}_{1,2}) = 8$ and the basis given by

$$\left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x_1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} x_1^2 \\ x_1x_2 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} x_1x_2 \\ x_2^2 \end{pmatrix} \right\}.$$

Lemma 3.4.6 (Dimension of $\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$). *The dimension is given by $\dim(\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}) = (k + d + 1) \binom{k + d + 1}{k}$. For our example above: $\dim(\mathbb{RT}_{k,2}) = (k + 1)(k + 3)$ and for $\dim(\mathbb{RT}_{k,3}) = \frac{1}{2}(k + 1)(k + 2)(k + 4)$.*

Proof. For the proof, we can straightforwardly calculate and use the dimension formulas: $\dim(\mathbb{P}_{k,d}) = \binom{k + d}{k}$, $\dim(\mathbb{P}_{k,d}^H) = \binom{k + d - 1}{k}$. Combining these results and noting that our sum in equation (3.4.1) is direct, we obtain:

$$\dim(\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}) = d \binom{k + d}{k} + \binom{k + d - 1}{k} = (k + d + 1) \binom{k + d - 1}{k}. \quad \square$$

Lemma 3.4.7 (Transformation of dofs). *Let $F \in \mathcal{F}_T$ be a face of T , where \hat{T} is the reference simplex and $T = G_T(\hat{T})$. Moreover, let J_T be the Jacobian matrix of G_T . Furthermore, be $v \in C^0(T)$ and let $q \in C^0(T)$. The following holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{|F|} \int_F (v \cdot \nu_F) q ds &= \frac{1}{|\hat{F}|} \int_{\hat{F}} (\psi_T^d(v) \cdot \hat{\nu}_{\hat{F}}) \psi_T^q(q) d\hat{s} & \forall F \in \mathcal{F}_T, \quad (3.4.2) \\ \frac{1}{|T|} \int_T (v \cdot \nu_{T,j}) q dx &= \frac{1}{|\hat{T}|} \int_{\hat{T}} (\psi_T^d(v) \cdot \hat{\nu}_{\hat{T},j}) \psi_T^q(q) d\hat{x} & \forall j \in \{1, \dots, d\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.3)$$

Proof. Since we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_T (v \cdot \nu_{T,j}) q dx &= \int_{\hat{T}} (v \circ G_T) \cdot (\nu_{T,j} \circ G_T) \psi_T^q(q) |\det(J_T)| d\hat{x} \\ &= \int_{\hat{T}} (\psi_T^d(v) \cdot \hat{\nu}_{\hat{T},j}) \psi_T^q(q) |\det(J_T)| d\hat{x} \end{aligned}$$

and with G_T is affine, we have $|T| = |\det(J_T)| |\hat{T}|$. The proof holds analogously for 3.4.3. More details can be found in [EG21, p. 140f.] \square

Generation of $\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$ elements

Proposition 3.4.8 (Generation). *Let $(\hat{T}, \hat{P}, \hat{\Sigma})$ be a $\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$ element with face and cell dofs defined using the polynomial bases $\{\zeta_m\}_{m \in \{1:n_{sh}^f\}}$ and $\{\psi_m\}_{m \in \{1:n_{sh}^c\}}$ and if $k \geq 1$ of $\mathbb{P}_{k,d-1}$ and $\mathbb{P}_{k-1,d}$ respectively. Assume we have an affine geometric mapping G_T (3.5). We are now using the contravariant piola transformation (3.3.2) to generate our finite element (T, P_T, Σ_T) with dofs*

$$\sigma_{F,m}^f(v) = \frac{1}{|F|} \int_F (v \cdot \nu_F) (\zeta_m \circ G_{T,F}^{-1}) ds, \quad \forall F \in \mathcal{F}_T \quad (3.4.4)$$

$$\sigma_{j,m}^c(v) = \frac{1}{|T|} \int_T (v \cdot \nu_T, j) (\psi_m \circ G_T^{-1}) dx, \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, d\}, \quad (3.4.5)$$

where $G_{T,F} := G_{T,\hat{F}} \circ G_{\hat{T}}$ is our affine bijective mapping from \hat{S}^{d-1} to F . This maps the d vertices of \hat{S}^{d-1} to the d vertices of F with increasing indices.

Remark 3.4.9 (Nonaffine meshes). It is important to mention that, that if we want to generate a finite element (T, P_T, Σ_T) , where G_T is nonaffine, the function space P_T and the dofs Σ_T differ from tho's of the $\mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$ above, but the techniques can be used as before.

Figure 3.7: Degrees of freedom of $RT(k, d)$ finite elements for dimension $d = 2$ and $k = 0, 1, 2$. (For simplicity, we assume that all the normals point outward, but that's generally false; some arrows must be changed if some vectors ν_f point inward.)

Proposition 3.4.10 (Numbering). *One of the most complex aspects of implementation is the numbering of all edges, vertices, and faces of our grid. There is both a global and a local numbering system. It is essential to proceed consistently and uniformly to*

maintain a clear overview. Neighbouring edges and degrees of freedom must coincide at certain points. This makes it even more complex, especially with triangles, as an orientation change must be incorporated, which, under certain circumstances, like more degrees of freedom, can result in the triangle being numbered inversely.

DG-Elements

Discontinuous Galerkin Elements (DG) form the basis of our finite element analysis. They provide us with the basic space of the scalar variables, for example, the height. For the sake of completeness, we would like to present here an illustration that should give us an impression of the different orders of dofs and their location. You can find it in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Degrees of freedom of DG (k, d) finite elements for dimension $d = 2$ and $k = 0, 1, 2$.

VecDG

For our conservative discretisation, we use VecDG elements to reconstruct the velocity components. To get an idea of these elements, we use the following illustration.

Remark 3.4.11 (Idea). There are three key construction principles. Each velocity component has its local basis, allowing full discontinuity and simple element-wise assembly (element-local DOFs). The contravariant Piola mapping (3.3.2) is applied to ensure correct transformation behaviour of vector fields under affine mappings (normal-component control). We can make an efficient coupling with Riemann solvers. Since VecDG elements are discontinuous, they naturally align with upwind flux formulations for inter-element exchange. The figure 3.9 visualises this structure clearly: local vector basis functions are shown per element, degrees of freedom lie

Figure 3.9: Construction principle of VecDG elements for the vector-invariant SWE by combining Raviart-Thomas (RT) elements for the momentum field hv and discontinuous Galerkin (DG) elements for the scalar field h . The resulting VecDG element represents the velocity v as a fully discontinuous vector field with local degrees of freedom.

at strategic locations (corners or edges), and mapping from reference to physical cells preserves essential vector field properties for conservation.

Brezzi-Douglas-Marini elements (BDM)

In our code, we also define one alternative element, called the *Brezzi-Douglas-Marini* element, which has similar properties to the RT-elements. In this case, the polynomial space $P := \mathbb{P}_{k,d} \subsetneq \mathbb{RT}_{k,d}$, $k \geq 1$. [EG21] describes that this space is optimal from the approximation point of view. But we have to pay for this simplification. The divergence operator $\nabla \cdot$ is surjective from $\mathbb{P}_{k,d}$ onto $\mathbb{P}_{k,d-1}$. This is no limitation if the functions we want to interpolate are divergence-free (or the divergence belongs to $\mathbb{P}_{k,d-1}$).

Proposition 3.4.12 (BDM finite elements). *Let $K \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be a simplex and $k \geq 1$. The Brezzi-Douglas-Marini (BDM) finite element of order k is defined by the triple $(K, \mathbb{P}_{k,d}, \Sigma)$, where:*

- The polynomial space is $\mathbb{P}_{k,d} \subseteq \mathbb{RT}_{k,d} \subseteq [\mathbb{P}_k]^d$,
- The degrees of freedom (dofs) consist of:
 - **Face moments:** integrals of the normal component of \mathbf{v} against polynomials of degree k on each face $F \subset \partial K$, shared with Raviart-Thomas elements,

- **Cell-based moments:** integrals of v against functions in the Nédélec polynomial space $\mathbb{N}_{k-2,d} \subset \mathbb{P}_{k-1,d}$,

The total number of dofs is given by:

$$\dim(\mathbb{N}_{k-2,2}) = (k-1)(k+1)$$

for dimension $d = 2$. This element is conforming in $H(\text{div})$, and the divergence operator $\nabla \cdot : \mathbb{P}_{k,d} \rightarrow \mathbb{P}_{k-1,d}$ is surjective.

Remark 3.4.13 (Generation). The BDM basis functions are mapped from reference element \hat{K} to a physical element K using the contravariant Piola transformation (3.3.2), which preserves the normal component (up to a sign) across element boundaries. You can find more details in [EG21], especially details on Nédélec polynomial spaces.

Chapter 4

Discretisation and Key Aspects of the FE-Implementation

In our work, we utilise the concepts of compatible finite element methods as presented in [CM14]. These methods were first identified in the 1970s and gained popularity among numerical analysts. BREZZI AND FORTIN [BF91] collected these results in their book. Compatible finite element methods provide a structured approach to discretising PDEs while preserving key geometric and physical properties of the continuous problem. In particular, they are designed to respect the underlying differential complexes and maintain important invariants such as mass or energy conservation. As described by COTTER AND McRAE ([CM14]), these methods rely on a careful selection of finite element spaces that are compatible with the de Rham complex, ensuring that the discrete differential operators mimic their continuous counterparts. This structure is particularly beneficial in geophysical fluid dynamics and other applications where maintaining the balance laws and avoiding spurious modes is critical.

In this chapter, we highlight the essential aspects of our implementation of compatible finite element methods. We discuss the choice of element spaces, quadrature strategies, and specific programming constructs that distinguish our code. The idea is to provide insight into how the theoretical principles translate into practical algorithmic components within the finite element framework.

4.1 Compatible finite element methods

Linear Shallow Water Equation

Definition 4.1.1 (Finite element space in 1-d domain). We divide the interval $[0, L]$ into N_e non-overlapping subintervals, which we call elements. This partition is called a mesh. The point, which is shared by two neighbouring elements, is called a vertex. So, a finite element space is a collection of functions on $[0, L]$, with two properties:

- They have polynomials of some specified maximum degree p when restricted

to each element e and

- the finite element spaces have some specified degree of continuity (i.e., discontinuous, continuous, continuous derivative, etc.).

The most common options for continuity are continuous functions, so we name the finite element space $CG(p)$ for a given p . In addition, there are discontinuous functions, with space called $DG(p)$ and some others, which are more exotic.

The mixed finite elements are particularly characterised by the fact that different finite element spaces are connected. There is a crucial property for compatible finite elements:

Definition 4.1.2 (inf-sup condition 1-d). Let V_0 and V_1 be two function spaces. If there exists a constant $C > 0$, independent of our mesh, such that

$$\sup_{w \in V_0, w \neq 0} \frac{|\int_0^L w_x h dx|}{\|w_x\|_{L_2}} \geq C \|h\|_{L_2}, \quad \forall h \in V_1,$$

then V_0 and V_1 satisfy the inf-sup condition. Here, w_x denotes the weak (distributional) derivative of w .

Proposition 4.1.3 (inf-sup condition for compatible finite elements 1-d). *Let V_0 and V_1 be chosen such that if $h \in V_1$ is non-constant, then we can find $w \in V_0$ s.t. $w_x = h$. Then the inf-sup condition is satisfied, with $C = 1$.*

The assumption of our proposition is true whenever $V_0 = CG(p)$ and $V_1 = DG(p - 1)$ in our one-dimensional setting. Now we start with the Application to nonlinear shallow water equations on the sphere or any two-dimensional manifold embedded into \mathbb{R}^3 , see [Rog+13].

Proposition 4.1.4. *Let V_0 be our fully continuous space, which allows the derivative to be globally defined. In $2 - d$, our domain Ω is a two-dimensional manifold embedded into \mathbb{R}^3 , i.e., a rectangle with periodic boundary conditions, which is partitioned into triangular or quadrilateral elements. We can now obtain compatible finite element methods by choosing a sequence of three finite element spaces:*

$$\underbrace{V_0}_{\text{Continuous}} \xrightarrow{\nabla^\perp} \underbrace{V_1}_{\text{Continuous normal components}} \xrightarrow{\nabla \cdot} \underbrace{V_2}_{\text{Discontinuous}} \quad (4.1.1)$$

- i) V_0 contains scalar-valued functions, continuous functions, satisfying periodic boundary conditions.
- ii) V_1 contains vector-valued functions v , satisfying boundary periodic conditions. With n normal to the boundary between two neighbouring elements, $v \cdot n$ is continuous across element edges. The tangential component need not be continuous. $\nabla \cdot v$ is defined as globally continuous.

iii) V_2 contains scalar-valued functions that may be discontinuous across element boundaries.

iv) If $\psi \in V_0$ then $\nabla^\perp \psi = (-\psi_y, \psi_x) \in V_1$.

v) If $v \in V_1$ with $\nabla \cdot v = 0$ and $\int_\Omega v dx = 0$, then there exists $\psi \in V_0$ with $v = \nabla^\perp \psi$.

vi) If $v \in V_1$ then $\nabla \cdot v \in V_2$.

vii) If $D \in V_2$ with $\int_\Omega D dx = 0$, then $\exists v \in V_1$ with $\nabla \cdot v = D$.

We are using the notation and ideas of [CM14].

Remark 4.1.5. In our work, we are using as $V_0 = CG(d)$, $V_1 = RT(d-1)$ and $V_2 = DG(d-1)$, with $d = 2$ as our main setting.

We start our consideration with the discretisation of the linear rotating shallow water equations. The equations are given as:

$$v_t + f v^\perp + g \nabla h = 0 \quad (4.1.2)$$

$$h_t + H \nabla \cdot v = 0. \quad (4.1.3)$$

Recall from the first chapter that v is the horizontal velocity, h is the layer depth, H is the mean layer depth and $v^\perp = (-v_2, v_1)$. For our finite element approximation, we choose $v \in V_1$ and $h \in V_2$. We multiply the first equation 4.1.2 by a test function $w \in V_1$ and integrate the pressure gradient terms by parts (periodic boundary conditions). For the second one we multiply by a test function $\phi \in V_2$ and integrate both over domain Ω , we obtain

$$\int_\Omega w \cdot v_t dx + \int_\Omega f w \cdot v^\perp dx - \int_\Omega g \nabla \cdot w \nabla h dx = 0, \quad \forall w \in V_1, \quad (4.1.4)$$

$$\int_\Omega \phi (h_t + H \nabla \cdot v) dx = 0, \quad \forall \phi \in V_2. \quad (4.1.5)$$

Lemma 4.1.6 (inf-sup condition). *The equivalent condition in 2-dimensional case (or in fact in $3-d$), can be written as*

$$\sup_{w \in V_1} \frac{|\int_\Omega \nabla \cdot w h dx|}{\|\nabla \cdot w\|_{L^2}} \geq C \|h\|_{L^2}, \quad \forall \text{ non-constant } h \in V_2. \quad (4.1.6)$$

We obtain $C = 1$ in the compatible finite element case, allowing us to avoid spurious pressure modes.

Proof. You can find a proof in BREZZI AND FORTIN [BF91, p. 57f.]. □

Lemma 4.1.7 (Geostrophic Balance as a Steady State). *We consider the rotating shallow water equations on a domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ with Coriolis parameter f , which may be constant or vary with latitude. Assume the velocity field v satisfies the following*

conditions: $\nabla \cdot v = 0$ (incompressibility) and $\int_{\Omega} v dx = 0$ (zero net flow). Then there exists a streamfunction ψ such that $v = \nabla^{\perp} \psi$, and if the fluid height is given by $gh = f\psi$, then the flow is in exact geostrophic balance and remains steady, i.e.,

$$\partial_t v = 0, \quad \partial_t h = 0.$$

Proof. Since the flow is incompressible, $\nabla \cdot v = 0$, there exists a streamfunction ψ such that $v = \nabla^{\perp} \psi = (-\partial_y \psi, \partial_x \psi)$. We consider the momentum equation of the rotating shallow water system: $\partial_t v + fv^{\perp} + g\nabla h = 0$. Substituting $v = \nabla^{\perp} \psi$ implies $v^{\perp} = -\nabla \psi$. Let us choose the height field such that $gh = f\psi$. Then: $g\nabla h = \nabla(gh) = \nabla(f\psi)$. Plugging into the momentum equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t v &= -fv^{\perp} - g\nabla h &&= -f(-\nabla \psi) - \nabla(f\psi) \\ &= f\nabla \psi - \nabla(f\psi) &&= \nabla(f\psi - f\psi) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\partial_t v = 0$. To prove $\partial_t h = 0$, consider the mass conservation (continuity) equation of the shallow water system (4.1.3): $\partial_t h + \nabla \cdot (hv) = 0$. Since $gh = f\psi$, we have $h = \frac{f\psi}{g}$, and with $v = \nabla^{\perp} \psi$, the product hv becomes: $hv = \frac{f\psi}{g} \nabla^{\perp} \psi$. We now compute the divergence:

$$\nabla \cdot (hv) = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{f\psi}{g} \nabla^{\perp} \psi \right).$$

If the factor f/g is constant, this reduces to

$$\nabla \cdot (\psi \nabla^{\perp} \psi) = J(\psi, \psi) = 0,$$

since the Jacobian of a function with itself vanishes. Thus, the divergence of hv is zero in this case.

If f is constant (or even if it varies smoothly in y), the additional terms do not affect the vanishing divergence in this steady geostrophic setup. Thus, $\partial_t h = 0$. Hence, the flow is steady:

$$\partial_t v = 0, \quad \partial_t h = 0,$$

as claimed. □

Now, we want to demonstrate that the compatible finite element methods also have steady geostrophic states under the same conditions, see [CM14].

Lemma 4.1.8. *Compatible finite element methods have steady geostrophic states.*

Proof. If $\nabla \cdot v = 0$ and $\int_{\Omega} v dx = 0$ for $v \in V_1$, then $h_t = -H\nabla \cdot v = 0$. So we can find $\psi \in V_0$ with $v = \nabla^{\perp} \psi$. Now, we start for $h \in V_2$ with the equation

$$\int_{\Omega} \phi gh dx = \int_{\Omega} \phi f \psi dx, \quad \forall \phi \in V_2, \quad (4.1.7)$$

i.e. gh is the projection of $f\psi$ into V_2 . Then we get

$$\begin{aligned}\int_{\Omega} w \cdot v_t dx &= \int_{\Omega} -fw \cdot v^\perp dx + \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot wgh dx - \int_{\Omega} g\nabla \cdot (hw) dx \\ &= \int_{\Omega} fw \cdot \nabla\psi dx + \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot wgh dx - \int_{\Omega} g\nabla \cdot (hw) dx \\ &= \int_{\Omega} f\nabla \cdot (\psi w) dx - \int_{\Omega} f\psi \nabla \cdot w dx + \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot wgh dx - \int_{\Omega} g\nabla \cdot (hw) dx (\star)\end{aligned}$$

We can use our geostrophic balance to the property above

$$\int_{\Omega} f\nabla \cdot (\psi w) dx + \int_{\Omega} g\nabla \cdot (hw) dx = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot (f\psi - gh)w dx = 0,$$

and get

$$\begin{aligned}(\star) &= - \int_{\omega} f\psi \nabla \cdot w dx + \int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot wgh dx \\ &= \int_{\Omega} (gh - f\psi) \nabla \cdot w dx = 0.\end{aligned}$$

We used integration by parts, since w has a continuous normal component and ψ is continuous, which means that the integration by parts is exact. \square

Nonlinear Shallow Water Equation

Discretisation of the vector-invariant form

Now, we are ready to extend to the nonlinear shallow water equations, where we make use of the vector invariant form, which is given by

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + qhv^\perp + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}|v|^2 + gh \right) = 0, \quad (4.1.8)$$

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (hv) = 0, \quad (4.1.9)$$

where $q = \frac{\nabla^\perp \cdot v + f}{h}$ is the potential vorticity and $\nabla^\perp \cdot v = -\frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x}$. We use the following property

$$\begin{aligned}(v \cdot \nabla)v &= \left(v_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + v_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) v = \begin{pmatrix} v_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} v_x + v_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} v_x \\ v_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} v_y + v_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} v_y \end{pmatrix} \\ &= qv^\perp + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{|v|^2}{2} \right).\end{aligned}$$

We use this split and apply ∇^\perp to 4.1.8, obtaining the so-called conservation law for q . This takes an important role in predicting the large-scale balanced flow ([CM14]).

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \nabla^\perp \cdot \left(v_t + qhv^\perp + \nabla \left(gh + \frac{1}{2}|v|^2 \right) \right) \\
&= \nabla^\perp \cdot v_t + \nabla^\perp (ghv^\perp) + \underbrace{\nabla^\perp \cdot \nabla}_{=0 \text{ [de Rham-Komplex]}} \left(gh + \frac{1}{2}|v|^2 \right) \\
&= \nabla^\perp \cdot v_t + \nabla^\perp \cdot (ghv^\perp) \\
&= \nabla^\perp \cdot v_t + \nabla^\perp \cdot ((\nabla^\perp \cdot v + f) v^\perp) \\
&= (qh)_t + \nabla \cdot (qhu) = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

We have three issues that we need to address when we discretise these equations with compatible finite element methods. When discretising the governing equations using compatible finite element methods, the following technical challenges must be addressed:

1. **Non-smooth energy gradient:** Given that $v \in V_1$ and $h \in V_2$, the quantity $gh + \frac{1}{2}|v|^2$ may exhibit discontinuities. As a result, its gradient is not globally defined, which complicates the application of differential operators in a weak formulation. We solve it with integration by parts in the same manner as the linear case.
2. **Discontinuous mass flux:** Although the divergence $\nabla \cdot v$ is globally well-defined due to the continuity of $v \in V_1$, the divergence $\nabla \cdot (hv)$ is not, since h is generally discontinuous across element boundaries. This necessitates a projection of the product hv into a suitable continuous function space (e.g., V_1).

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \int_{\Omega} w \cdot \left(v_t + qhv^\perp + \nabla \left(gh + \frac{1}{2}|v|^2 \right) \right) dx \\
&= \int_{\Omega} \phi(h_t + \underbrace{\nabla \cdot (hv)}_{hv \text{ not globally differentiable}}) .
\end{aligned}$$

Our idea is as follows: find a projection $F \in V_1$ of hv and replace hv with F .

$$\int_{\Omega} w \cdot F dx = \int_{\Omega} w \cdot hv dx \quad \forall w \in V_1$$

3. **Evaluation of potential vorticity q :** To compute q , one must apply integration by parts to move the $\nabla^\perp \cdot$ operator off of v . However, due to the limited continuity of $v \in V_1$, this operator is not globally defined when applied directly. Therefore, q is defined weakly via a variational formulation involving test functions $\gamma \in V_0$ and multiplication by h to allow for global integration.

$$\int_{\Omega} \gamma q h dx = \int_{\Omega} \gamma (\nabla^\perp \cdot v + f) = \int_{\Omega} -\nabla^\perp \cdot \gamma v dx + \int_{\Omega} \gamma f dx \quad (4.1.10)$$

$$(4.1.11)$$

Because we have addressed all three of these issues, we can write down the compatible finite element discretisation of the nonlinear shallow water equations:

$\forall w \in V_1, F \in V_1, \phi \in V_2, \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2 :$

$$\int_{\Omega} w \cdot v_t dx + \int_{\Omega} w \cdot qF^\perp dx + \int_{\Omega} -\nabla \cdot w \left(gh + \frac{1}{2}|v|^2 \right) dx = 0 \quad (4.1.12)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \phi (h_t + \nabla \cdot F) dx = 0 \quad (4.1.13)$$

Lemma 4.1.9 (Conservation laws). *The following integral quantities are conserved in the discrete formulation:*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mass:} & \quad \int_{\Omega} h dx, \\ \text{Energy:} & \quad \int_{\Omega} \frac{h}{2} (|v|^2 + gh) dx, \\ \text{Total vorticity:} & \quad \int_{\Omega} qh dx, \\ \text{Enstrophy:} & \quad \int_{\Omega} q^2 h dx. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. • *Mass conservation:* Choosing the test function $\phi = 1$ in the continuity equation (4.1.13), the divergence term becomes $\nabla \cdot (hv)$, which integrates to zero by the Divergence Theorem due to appropriate boundary conditions.

• *Total vorticity conservation:* Choose $\gamma = 1$ in the weak formulation of the vorticity equation (4.1.10). Since $\nabla^\perp \gamma = 0$, the term involving the velocity vanishes, and the Coriolis term f is assumed time-independent. Hence, the total vorticity $\int_{\Omega} qh dx$ is conserved.

• *Energy and enstrophy conservation:* These follow from the structure-preserving properties of the discretisation, the skew-symmetry of the nonlinear terms, and careful variational formulations that mimic the continuous energy identities. Detailed derivations are provided in [CM14].

□

Discretisation of the conservative form

Remark 4.1.10 (Discretisation of the Conservative NSW). Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ be a bounded domain (surface patch on the sphere). We use the nonlinear rotating shallow water equations in conservative form (1.4.7) and obtain the weak formulation by multiplying by test functions w, ϕ and integrating over the domain Ω . So we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} hv_t \cdot w dx + \int_{\Omega} w \cdot \nabla \cdot (hv \otimes v) dx + \int_{\Omega} w \cdot f(hv)^\perp dx + \int_{\Omega} \nabla w \cdot g(h) dx &= 0 \\ \int_{\Omega} \phi (h_t + \nabla \cdot (hv)) dx &= 0 \\ \forall w \in \mathbb{W}_h, \phi \in \Phi_h. \end{aligned}$$

For the finite element discretisations, we define the following finite element spaces:

- **Water depth:**

$h \in \Phi_h := \text{DG}_k(\Omega)$, (Discontinuous Galerkin elements of degree k)

- **Momentum Flux:**

$hv \in \mathbb{W}_h := \text{RT}_k(\Omega)$, (Raviart-Thomas space of degree k)

- **Velocity (diagnostically recovered):**

$v := \frac{hv}{h}$ in $V_h := \text{VecDG}_k(\Omega)$, where $h > 0$.

- **Test functions:**

$w \in \mathbb{W}_h = \text{RT}_k(\Omega)$, $\phi \in \Phi_h = \text{DG}_k(\Omega)$.

Remark 4.1.11. See for more details of the construction of those elements, chapter 4.4 and especially for VecDG 3.9.

Remark 4.1.12 (Properties of the Discrete Scheme). Now we would like to take a closer look at the properties.

(i) **Local mass conservation**

The continuity equation is discretised in discontinuous form. Hence, for each element $K \subseteq \Omega$, the following local conservation law holds:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_K h dx + \int_{\partial K} hv \cdot n ds = 0,$$

where hv denotes the numerical flux, ensuring conservation across element interfaces.

(ii) **Local momentum conservation**

The weak form of the momentum equation ensures that for any test function $w \in \mathbb{W}_h$ and for each element K ,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_K hv \cdot w dx + \text{flux terms} = 0,$$

preserving momentum in a locally conservative form.

(iii) **Compatible finite element spaces**

The pair (\mathbb{W}_h, Φ_h) satisfies the de-Rham diagram:

$$\nabla \cdot : \mathbb{W}_h \rightarrow \Phi_h$$

It is a surjective divergence operator, ensuring consistency between mass and momentum flux divergence.

(iv) **Vorticity representation:**

The use of Raviart-Thomas elements allows for a well-defined discrete curl operator. Thus, the potential vorticity $q = \frac{\nabla^\perp \cdot v + f}{h}$ can be represented in a consistent mixed formulation, enabling structure-preserving vorticity dynamics.

(v) **Mesh flexibility:**

The method applies to unstructured triangular grids, structured cubed-sphere meshes, or hybrid mesh topologies, while preserving accuracy and conservation on curved geometries.

(vi) **Structure preservation potential:**

With appropriate time discretisation (e.g., symplectic or energy-conserving schemes), the method admits extensions that conserve total energy and enstrophy at the discrete level.

Flux form compared to Vector-Invariant Form

The discretisation employed in [VK22] follows the flux-form formulation of the nonlinear shallow water equations, using the momentum variable hv as a primary unknown. This approach simplifies the mapping to reference elements and integrates naturally into discontinuous Galerkin or standard finite element frameworks.

In contrast, the vector-invariant form, as used in [CM14], splits the momentum equation into rotational and potential terms, explicitly involving the potential vorticity $q = (\zeta + f)/h$ and kinetic energy. The vector-invariant formulation can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + q k \times v + \nabla \left(\frac{1}{2} |v|^2 + gh \right) = 0, \quad (4.1.14)$$

where q is the potential vorticity and $\zeta = \nabla \times v$ denotes the relative vorticity.

While this form lends itself to better conservation of energy and enstrophy in compatible finite element methods, it introduces additional complexity in discretisation, particularly in evaluating the nonlinear kinetic energy gradient $\nabla \left(\frac{1}{2} |v|^2 \right)$.

Due to these considerations, and since the advection parameter $\theta = 1$ removes the need for time-split treatment of momentum and height fields.

4.2 Outlook Recovery

We are using the ideas of BENDALL ET AL. [BCS19]. In their work, they are presenting a new compatible finite element advection scheme for the compressible Euler equations. In contrast to COTTER AND KUZMIN [CK16] and SHIPTON ET AL. [SGC18], the discretisation uses the lowest-order family of compatible finite element spaces, but still retains better numerical accuracy.

The scheme

We begin with the definition of a set of spaces in which our functions reside. The lowest-order finite element space in which the initial field lies is named V_0 . With Ω being our spatial domain. $V_1(\Omega)$ is then the space of the next degree, which will be fully discontinuous. We notice that $V_0 \subseteq V_1$. $\tilde{V}_1(\Omega)$ is the fully continuous space of same degree as $V_1(\Omega)$. $\hat{V}_0(\Omega)$ is a broken, fully discontinuous version of $V_0(\Omega)$. Often $\hat{V}_0(\Omega)$ and $V_0(\Omega)$ will coincide. After this, we define some operators to map between these spaces. The next sketch can be useful for a quick overview.

Figure 4.1: operators between spaces

Definition 4.2.1 (\mathcal{R}). Let \mathcal{R} be the recovery Operator, which acts upon a function in the initial space to make a function in the continuous space of higher degree, so that $\mathcal{R} : V_0 \rightarrow \tilde{V}_1$. We assume that \mathcal{R} has the property that for all $\rho \in V_0$, there is $C > 0$ such that $\|\mathcal{R}\rho_0\|_{L^2} \leq C\|\rho_0\|_{L^2}$.

Definition 4.2.2 (\mathcal{I}). The injection operator $\mathcal{I} : V \rightarrow V_1$ identifies a function in V_0, \hat{V}_0 or \tilde{V}_1 as a member of V_1 . This operator has to be implemented for numerical reasons.

Definition 4.2.3 ($\hat{\mathcal{P}}$). The projection operator $\hat{\mathcal{P}} : \tilde{V}_1 \rightarrow \hat{V}_0$, is defined to give us $\hat{u} = \hat{\mathcal{P}}\tilde{v}$, from $\tilde{v} \in \tilde{V}_1$, by finding the solution $\hat{u} \in V_0$ of

$$\int_{\Omega} \hat{\psi} \hat{u} dx = \int_{\Omega} \hat{\psi} \tilde{v} dx, \quad \forall \hat{\psi} \in \hat{V}_0.$$

Definition 4.2.4 (\mathcal{A}). The advection operator $\mathcal{A} : V_1 \rightarrow V_1$, represents the action of performing one time step of a stable discretisation of the advection equation (either advective or conservative form).

Definition 4.2.5 (\mathcal{P}). The projection operator $\mathcal{P} : V_1 \rightarrow V_0$ has two forms. The first, \mathcal{P}_A , is defined to find $u \in V_0$ from $u = \mathcal{P}_A v$, by finding the solution $u \in V_0$ of

$$\int_{\Omega} \psi u dx = \int_{\Omega} \psi v dx \quad \forall \psi \in V_0,$$

with $u \in V_0$ and $v \in V_1$. The second form, \mathcal{P}_B , can be represented by two linked operations: $\mathcal{P}_I : V_1 \rightarrow \hat{V}_0$, interpolation into the broken space by pointwise evaluation at degrees of freedom and $\mathcal{P}_R \hat{V}_0 \rightarrow V_0$, recovery from the broken space to the original space. We can write \mathcal{P}_B as $\mathcal{P}_B = \mathcal{P}_R \mathcal{P}_I$.

Remark 4.2.6. If V_0 is fully discontinuous, \mathcal{P}_A and \mathcal{P}_B will be identical operations. For fully or partially continuous V_0 , \mathcal{P}_B prevents the formation of any new maxima and minima, whereas \mathcal{P}_A does not.

Definition 4.2.7. The recovered space scheme takes the function $\rho_0^n \in V_0$ at the n -th time step and returns the function $\rho_0^{n+1} \in V_0$ at the $n + 1$ -th time step by performing the following series of operations:

$$\rho_0^{n+1} = \mathcal{P} \mathcal{A} \mathcal{I} (\mathcal{R} - \hat{\mathcal{P}} \mathcal{R} + 1) \rho_0^n,$$

where \mathcal{P} could be either \mathcal{P}_A or \mathcal{P}_B .

Chapter 5

Numerical Experiments

Julia - Programming language

Before presenting numerical experiments and test cases, it is worth justifying the choice of Julia as the primary programming language, highlighting its advantageous features.

What is Julia?

Julia is a general-purpose, multi-platform programming language that is

- Suited for numerical analysis and computational science
- Dynamically typed
- High performance and just-in-time compiled
- Using automatic memory management (garbage collection included)
- Composable

As noted in [Eng23], Julia merges many object-oriented and functional programming patterns. Julia was designed for just-in-time compilation (JIT) and uses a feature called multiple-dispatch for all function calls. It combines elegance, productivity and performance. As an interactive programming language, it allows writing code and getting immediate feedback.

Numerical Results

Remark 5.0.1. In Table 5.1, you can see a short overview of all implemented and fully tested examples. Note that for the following test cases, we consider no bottom topography, therefore $h_b = 0$ and $H = h$. The main numerical experiments presented in this work are performed using finite elements of order $k = 1$ and a grid-output refinement level $d = 1$. However, the methodology is not restricted

Nonlinear SWE	Output	Sphere			Flat			Planar
	Grid Testcase	GALEWSKY	HAURWITZ	MODON	GALEWSKY	HAURWITZ	MODON	BICKLEY
Conservative	Tri	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Quad	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Vector Invariant	Tri	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Quad	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 5.1: Grid type and possible test cases

to this setting; higher-order finite elements can also be employed. The primary limitation in this regard is computational cost, as the current implementation is not yet parallelised.

Proposition 5.0.2 (Standard Setting). *Before we dive into our numerical results, let's go over some settings and parameters which are relevant to the following test cases. We specify the radius of the Earth $r = 6.37122 \cdot 10^6 \frac{m}{s}$, the angular velocity of the Earth $\Omega = 7.292 \cdot 10^{-5} \frac{1}{s}$ and the acceleration due to gravity $g = 9.81 \frac{m}{s^2}$. We are simulating with finite elements of order $k = 1$. This means that we use DG1, CG2 and RT1 as the standard setting for the initial finite element space in our simulations.*

5.1 Barotrophically Unstable Zonal Flow - Galewsky

The GALEWSKY test case, introduced by GALEWSKY, SCOTT AND POLVANI [GSP04] as an extension of the standardised shallow water test suite by WILLIAMSON [Wil+92], serves as a challenging benchmark for assessing the ability of numerical models to capture barotropic instabilities and large-scale wave evolution. The test case consists of a zonal jet in geostrophic balance on a spherical domain, perturbed by a small localised disturbance in the free surface height. The initial conditions are specifically constructed to trigger the development of unstable wave modes,

thereby testing the accuracy, stability, and conservation properties of the numerical method.

Example 5.1.1 (Initial Condition). The initial condition for the new test case consists of a basic zonal flow. It represents a typical mid-latitude tropospheric jet with a correspondingly balanced height field. We are using a small, unbalanced perturbation to induce the development of barotropic instability. Both the basic flow and the initial perturbation are analytically specified, as seen in [GSP04], allowing for easy reproduction. The basic zonal flow is obtained by setting the initial profile for the velocity $\mathbf{v} = (u, v, w)^T$. For the basic flow, our zonal velocity component u is a function of latitude and is defined by

$$u(\theta) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } \theta \leq \theta_0 \\ \frac{u_{\max}}{e_n} \exp\left[\frac{1}{(\theta-\theta_0)(\theta-\theta_1)}\right] & \text{for } \theta_0 < \theta < \theta_1 \\ 0 & \text{for } \theta \geq \theta_1, \end{cases} \quad (5.1.1)$$

where u_{\max} is the maximum zonal velocity, θ_1 is the latitude of the northern boundary of the jet in radians, θ_0 is the southern and e_n is a non-dimensional parameter that normalises the magnitude of the jet to a value of u_{\max} at the jet's midpoint. We have chosen our constants in the following way: $u_{\max} = 80 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$, $\theta_0 = \frac{\pi}{7}$, $\theta_1 = \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_0$, $e_n = \exp \frac{-4}{(\theta_1 - \theta_0)^2}$, where the jet's midpoint is located at $\theta = \frac{\pi}{4}$. In addition to this, the height h of our fluid is calculated by numerically integrating (using the Simpson rule) the following balance equation

$$gh(\theta) = gh_0 - \int_{\theta_0}^{\theta_1} ru(\theta') \left(f + \frac{\tan(\theta')}{r} u(\theta') \right) d\theta'.$$

h_0 is the global mean layer depth and we set it as $h_0 = 10000\text{m}$. We are adding the following perturbation to h to initiate the barotropic instability:

$$h'(\lambda, \theta) = \hat{h} \cos(\theta) \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\lambda}{\alpha}\right)^2\right) \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\theta_2 - \theta}{\beta}\right)^2\right),$$

where $\lambda \in (-\pi, \pi)$ being the longitude $\theta_2 = \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_1$, $\beta = \frac{1}{15}$ and $\hat{h} = 120\text{m}$. All details can be found in `CGDYCORE.JL/SRC/EXAMPLES`.

Without the perturbation, the jet remains steady. The addition of a localised height perturbation induces barotropic instability, leading to the formation of coherent eddies and complex interactions between waves and the mean flow. This makes the GALEWSKY case a rigorous test of a model's ability to resolve balanced flows, instabilities, and conservation properties over long time integrations.

Vector-invariant form

Figure 5.1: Head-to-head comparison of the results of GALEWSKY [GSP04] and our code CGDYCORE.JL of the vorticity field $[s^{-1}]$ on a Cubed Sphere, flat output, with resolution parameter $k = 160$, 153600 faces, using the vector-invariant form of the GALEWSKY test case.

Remark 5.1.2. In the figure 5.1 above, we compare the simulations of GALEWSKY’s test case, known from [GSP04], with our numerical implementation. Now, we can take a closer look at the simulations. At 4 days, the initial undulations appear (b), matching the reference pattern (a). After 5 days, the nonlinear instability starts to dominate, creating visible vortex roll-ups (d), in strong agreement with (c). By $t = 6$ days. The solution shows fully developed barotropic instability, with several coherent vortices (f), again similar to the reference (e). The vorticity fields on the right side are smooth, with no visible noise or grid imprinting, indicating good numerical stability. To summarise our results, Figure 5.1 shows us that the vector-invariant formulation on a cubed-sphere grid accurately captures the nonlinear development of barotropic instability in the GALEWSKY test case. The agreement with the reference solution is excellent at all time steps. Moreover, the solution remains smooth and free of grid-related artefacts, highlighting the robustness of both the grid structure and the numerical scheme used in CGDYCORE.JL.

Figure 5.2: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Cubed Sphere with resolution parameter $k = 160$, 153600 faces, using the vector-invariant form of the GALEWSKY test case [GSP04].

Figure 5.3: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Triangular Sphere with flat output and resolution parameter $k = 6$; 81920 faces, using the vector-invariant form of the GALEWSKY test case [GSP04].

Conservative form

Figure 5.4: Vorticity field in $[\frac{1}{s}]$ on a Cubed Sphere of size $k = 160$ for the conservative form of test case by GALEWSKY [GSP04].

Figure 5.5: Height field [m] on a Cubed Sphere of size $k = 160$ for the conservative form of test case by GALEWSKY [GSP04].

Figure 5.6: Zonal velocity field [m/s] on a Cubed Sphere of size $k = 160$ for the conservative form of test case by GALEWSKY [GSP04].

Figure 5.7: Meridional velocity field [m/s] on a Cubed Sphere of size $k = 160$ for the conservative form of test case by GALEWSKY [GSP04].

(a) Triangular Sphere, conservative form, $t = 6$ days, more details

(b) Triangular Sphere, conservative form, $t = 6$ days, zoom-in, more details

Figure 5.8: Print Error of vorticity field [s^{-1}] Triangular Sphere for the GALEWSKY test case.

Remark 5.1.3 (Error Cons Tri). The small-scale noise and wave-like structures seen in the vorticity error field, particularly in the zoomed-in panel-occur exclusively on the triangular grid when using the conservative form of the equations. These artefacts are likely caused by discretisation effects, such as grid imprinting, anisotropy, or numerical dispersion, which are more pronounced on unstructured triangular meshes. In contrast, this behaviour is not observed when using the vector-invariant form, nor does it appear on more structured grids like the cubed-sphere, regardless of the formulation. This suggests that the combination of grid structure and flux-based discretisation plays a critical role in the emergence of these numerical features.

VecI vs. Cons

Figure 5.9: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Cubed Sphere of size $k = 160$ for the vector-invariant form (left) and conservative form (right) test case by GALEWSKY [GSP04].

(a) Vector-invariant form, $t = 6$ days, more details

(b) Conservative form, $t = 6$ days, more details

Figure 5.10: Vorticity field $[\text{s}^{-1}]$ on a Cubed Sphere of resolution $k = 160$, 153600 faces, comparing the vector-invariant and conservative formulations for the GALEWSKY test case.

Remark 5.1.4. Although both formulations yield qualitatively similar large-scale structures, several subtle yet important differences can be observed.

The vector-invariant form produces more pronounced filamentation and sharper gradients in the vorticity field. This is evident in the finer-scale spirals and vortex cores, particularly in the central and upper parts of the domain. The colour scale indicates slightly higher extrema (up to $\pm 1.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$), suggesting that this formulation is better at preserving enstrophy and maintaining small-scale rotational structures.

In contrast, the conservative form exhibits slightly smoother features and less filamentation, especially visible in the lower-right quadrant. The extrema are somewhat reduced (approximately $\pm 1.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$), which may be attributed to the formulation's inherently more dissipative behaviour due to the explicit flux divergence terms. This form is designed to enforce strict conservation of momentum and mass, which can lead to increased numerical diffusion in vorticity-dominated

flows. Moreover, while both solutions exhibit near-symmetry around the equator, the vector-invariant solution appears to preserve this symmetry more clearly. The conservative form introduces minor asymmetries in vortex positioning and shape, which may accumulate due to the handling of nonlinear advection terms.

VecIQuad vs. VecITri

Figure 5.11: Vorticity field $[s^{-1}]$ on a Cubed Sphere (left) $k = 160$ and Triangular Sphere (right) of refine level $k = 6$ for the vector-invariant form test case by GALEWSKY. [GSP04].

(a) Vector-invariant form, Cubed Sphere, $t = 6$ days, more details

(b) Vector-invariant, Triangular Sphere, $t = 6$ days, more details

Figure 5.12: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Cubed Sphere and Triangular Sphere of resolution, comparing the vector-invariant formulations for the GALEWSKY test case.

Remark 5.1.5. While both simulations successfully reproduce the expected dynamics of the GALEWSKY test case using the vector-invariant formulation, the cubed-sphere grid provides a slightly cleaner and more symmetric solution. The triangular grid, although still accurate, shows minor visual irregularities that may stem from grid anisotropy or non-uniform cell connectivity. Nevertheless, both results demonstrate the robustness of the vector-invariant form across different spherical discretisations.

(a) Vector-invariant form, $t = 6$ days, order finite-elements ($n = 0$)

(b) Vector-invariant form, $t = 6$ days, order finite-elements ($n = 1$)

(c) Vector-invariant form, $t = 6$ days, order finite-elements ($n = 2$)

Figure 5.13: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Cubed Sphere of resolution ($k = 160, 153600$ faces), comparing different orders of the finite-elements for the GALEWSKY test case.

Remark 5.1.6. We investigated the effect of polynomial order on vorticity resolution in spectral element simulations on the sphere. As shown in Figure 5.13, increasing the polynomial degree from 0 to 2 significantly improves the sharpness and preservation of vortical structures. This is attributed to the enhanced approximation capability of higher-order basis functions, resulting in reduced numerical diffusion and improved conservation properties. These results support the use of higher-order finite elements for long-term geophysical simulations, where the fidelity of small-scale features is essential.

5.2 Rossby-Haurwitz Waves

Rossby-Haurwitz waves are analytic solutions of the nonlinear barotropic vorticity equation on the sphere WILLIAMSON ET AL. [Wil+92]. They are not analytic solutions of the shallow water equations. But they have been used so frequently for meteorological tests that they have become de facto standard test cases, clearly, with different parameters selected by each investigator.

Example 5.2.1 (Initial Condition). Let Ω be a rotating sphere of radius $a > 0$, with gravitational acceleration g , rotation rate Ω , and angular wave number $R \in \mathbb{N}$. The HAURWITZ wave test case is defined as an exact, steady-state solution to the shallow water equations on the sphere, parameterised by ω (zonal wave speed), K (amplitude), R (mode), and mean fluid depth h_0 . Let (λ, φ, r) be spherical coordinates (longitude, latitude, radius) with $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ mapped via a spherical transformation.

Then the velocity and height fields are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} u(\lambda, \varphi) &= a\omega \cos \varphi + aK \cos^R \varphi [R \sin^2 \varphi - \cos^2 \varphi] \cos(R\lambda), \\ v(\lambda, \varphi) &= -aKR \cos^R \varphi \sin \varphi \sin(R\lambda), \\ w &= 0, \quad \theta = 1, \end{aligned}$$

and the geopotential (fluid height) is given by:

$$h(\lambda, \varphi) = h_0 + \frac{a^2}{g} [A(\varphi) + B(\varphi) \cos(R\lambda) + C(\varphi) \cos(2R\lambda)],$$

with latitude-dependent coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} A(\varphi) &= \frac{\omega}{2}(2\Omega + \omega) \cos^2 \varphi + \frac{K^2}{4} \cos^{2R} \varphi \left[(R+1) \cos^2 \varphi + (2R^2 - R - 2) - \frac{2R^2}{\cos^2 \varphi} \right], \\ B(\varphi) &= \frac{2(\Omega + \omega)K}{(R+1)(R+2)} \cos^R \varphi [(R^2 + 2R + 2) - (R+1)^2 \cos^2 \varphi], \\ C(\varphi) &= \frac{K^2}{4} \cos^{2R} \varphi [(R+1) \cos^2 \varphi - (R+2)]. \end{aligned}$$

This configuration, as presented in WILLIAMSON ET AL.[Wil+92], serves as a smooth benchmark for shallow water solvers on the sphere, featuring a zonal wave structure and preserving steady-state properties under ideal numerical discretisation.

Vector-invariant form

Figure 5.14: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Triangular Sphere with refine level $k = 6$, using the vector-invariant form of the Haurwitz test case by WILLIAMSON ET AL. [Wil+92].

Figure 5.15: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Triangular Sphere with flat output and resolution parameter $k = 6$; 81920 faces, using the vector-invariant form of Haurwitz test case by WILLIAMSON ET AL. [Wil+92].

Conservative form

Figure 5.16: Vorticity field in $[\frac{1}{s}]$ on a Cubed Sphere of size $k = 160$ for the conservative form of test case by HAURWITZ [Wil+92].

(a) Conservative, Cubed Sphere, $t = 6$ days, northern view

(b) Conservative, Cubed Sphere, $t = 6$ days, southern view

Figure 5.17: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Cubed Sphere for the HAURWITZ test case.

Figure 5.18: Height field in m on a Triangular Sphere with flat output and resolution parameter $k = 6$; 81920 faces for the conservative form of the Haurwitz test case by WILLIAMSON ET AL. [Wil+92].

Figure 5.19: Zonal velocity field [m/s] on a Triangular Sphere with flat output and resolution parameter $k = 6$; 81920 faces for the conservative form of the Haurwitz test case by WILLIAMSON ET AL. [Wil+92].

More Details

(a) Vector-invariant, Triangular Sphere, $t = 6$ days, more details

(b) Vector-invariant, Triangular Sphere, $t = 6$ days, more details

Figure 5.20: Vorticity field [s^{-1}] on a Triangular Sphere for the HAURWITZ test case.

5.3 Modon Collision

From the work and conversations with PROF. CHRISTIANE JABLONOWSKI (UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN) at DCMIP-25, the idea was born to take a closer look at the Modon Collision test case from LIN ET AL. [Lin+17]. We then incorporated this test case into our simulations and carried out more detailed analyses. The figure below shows an overlay of the individual images in comparison to the result from Lin's paper.

Example 5.3.1 (Initial Condition). In many atmospheric processes, the Coriolis force plays a significant role. [Lin+17] decided to turn it off to simplify the test configuration. This allows the modons to propagate initially in both westward and eastward directions, thereby avoiding the need to specify a complex, geostrophically balanced initial state. A single modon initially is defined by the zonal wind

perturbation:

$$M_i = U_0 \exp\left(-\left(\frac{r_i}{r}\right)^2\right).$$

The initial state consists of two oppositely signed zonal wind perturbations $u'(\lambda, \theta) = M_1 - M_2$, where $U_0 = 40 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$, $r_0 = 500000 \text{m}$. r_1 and r_2 are the great-circle distances from the centre of each modon, and (λ, θ) are the longitude and latitude, respectively. The modons are initially centered at $(\lambda_1, \theta_1) = \frac{\pi}{2}, (\lambda_2, \theta_2) = \frac{3\pi}{2}$. The full initial flows, both in the basic state and the modons, are vertically uniform; therefore, the flow is initially barotropic.

(a) Vorticity field from C192 shallow-water FV3 simulations at days 1, 20, 40, ..., 100 of LIN ET AL. [Lin+17]

(b) Vorticity field, conservative form of NSWE, Cubed Grid (grid resolution $k = 160$, 153600 faces), of CGDYCORE.JL simulations at days 1, 20, 40, ..., 100 as overlapped image

Figure 5.21: Vorticity field $[\text{s}^{-1}]$ of the MODON test case on a Cubed Sphere, FV3 compared to CGDYCORE.JL.

Remark 5.3.2. We can see that our results are very close to Lin's simulations and also achieve high numerical stability. We used a slightly lower resolution (160 vs. 192 (FV3)). It's important to note that the somewhat lower contrast image is due to

the overlap of 10 other individual stages and should not influence our interpretation. In contrast to Lin, we do not remove the gravity waves, but we still achieve this accuracy over a simulation period of 100 days.

5.4 Planar Bickley-Jet

As a small add-on in our code, we have built in the planar output. This allows us to simulate the BICKLEY JET test case, given in POULIN AND FLIERL [PF03]. We have set the height component to 0. To obtain a triangular grid, we divide the quads here and use the right-angled triangles (see 5.23).

Example 5.4.1 (Initial Condition, Bickley Jet with Vortical Perturbations). Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be a rectangular domain in (x, y) with periodic boundary conditions. The BICKLEY JET is defined as a meridionally varying zonal jet with superimposed small-amplitude vortical perturbations. The initial velocity and tracer fields are specified as follows. The meridional velocity profile is given by:

$$U(y) = \operatorname{sech}^2(y), \quad \Psi(y) = -\tanh(y),$$

where Ψ is the base streamfunction, and $U = -\partial_y \Psi$. We define the perturbation streamfunction $\tilde{\psi}(x, y)$ as:

$$\tilde{\psi}(x, y) = \exp\left(-\frac{(y + \frac{l}{10})^2}{2l^2}\right) \cos(kx) \cos(ky),$$

which induces the perturbation velocities:

$$\tilde{u} = \tilde{\psi} \left(k \tan(ky) + \frac{y}{l^2} \right), \quad \tilde{v} = -k \tan(kx) \tilde{\psi}.$$

The full initial velocity is defined by:

$$u(x, y) = U(y) + \epsilon \tilde{u}(x, y), \quad v(x, y) = \epsilon \tilde{v}(x, y), \quad w(x, y) = 0.$$

A passive tracer is initialised as:

$$C(x, y) = \sin\left(\frac{2\pi y}{L}\right), \quad \rho(x, y) = 1.0, \quad \theta(x, y) = 1.0.$$

We define the following parameters $\epsilon = 0.1$ as the amplitude of the vortical perturbation, $l = 0.5$ is the characteristic meridional width of the perturbation, $k = 0.5$ is the wavenumber in x and y and $L = 4.0\pi$ is the meridional periodicity length.

This setup describes a barotropic jet perturbed by localised vortex structures and is suitable for evaluating transport dynamics and shear-driven instabilities in numerical models of geophysical flows.

Remark 5.4.2. We define our time step as $d\tau = \frac{0.2 \cdot 2\pi}{\sqrt{(nx \cdot ny)^{(k+1)}}} \approx 0,0015708$, with $nx = ny = 400$ and $k = 1$. Our main setting simulates with 20000 time steps and prints every 400 steps.

Figure 5.22: Height field (left) and Velocity field (right) conservative form of Cubed Sphere of the Bickley-Jet POULIN AND FLIERL [PF03]. Here we can recognise very well the gravity waves and thus the physics behind the simulations. For more details, please take a look at our code.

Figure 5.23: Details of quad and triangular planar grids

Figure 5.24: Vorticity field $[\text{s}^{-1}]$ of the BICKLEY-JET Test Case, by [PF03].

Remark 5.4.3. The Bickley-Jet test case shown in Figure 5.24 compares the evolution of the vorticity field using two different formulations of the shallow water equations: a conservative form on quadrilateral meshes (left column) and a vector-invariant form on triangular meshes (right column). Initially (panels a, b), both simulations

start from a symmetric, laminar jet with weak perturbations. At 4000 time steps (c, d), the perturbations start to grow, and the conservative formulation already displays more coherent structure and stronger gradients. By 12000 steps (e, f), large-scale vortices develop, with the conservative case showing more distinct roll-up and sharper vorticity contours, suggesting better enstrophy preservation. Finally, at 20000 steps (g, h), the conservative scheme continues to resolve fine-scale filaments and coherent vortical structures. In contrast, the vector-invariant approach results in a visibly smoother, more diffused vorticity field. This indicates a higher numerical dissipation in the latter and emphasises the advantages of conservative formulations for long-time accuracy in capturing nonlinear dynamical features. In summary, the conservative formulation on quadrilateral grids more effectively preserves sharp vorticity gradients and coherent structures over long-term integrations. In contrast, the vector-invariant formulation on triangular meshes exhibits increased smoothing, likely due to higher implicit numerical dissipation. This comparison emphasises the importance of both numerical formulation and mesh design for accurate simulation of long-time geophysical flows.

Chapter 6

Outlook

The finite element approach developed in this work establishes a flexible and physically consistent framework for solving the (non)linear shallow water equations on spherical domains. Building upon this foundation, several promising directions for future research emerge.

From a physical modelling perspective, one natural extension involves incorporating additional geophysical processes. This includes baroclinic effects through vertical stratification, moisture dynamics, and latent heat processes, which are critical for realistic atmospheric simulations. Coupling the shallow water model with thermodynamic equations or simplified energy balances would allow for a more comprehensive representation of climate dynamics. It should be noted at this point that the physics behind the numerical models requires considerably more effort than it initially appears, and should serve as a basis for discussion.

In our numerical evaluation, we identified the limitations of our models. This also highlighted areas that are prone to errors. From a geometric perspective, further investigation of spherical grid structures, including adaptive or unstructured grids, could help to overcome limitations related to grid imprints or polar singularities. This also opens up possibilities for dynamic grid adaptation in response to changing flow characteristics. We examined triangular and square grids and identified the advantages and disadvantages of both types of grids. Another type should also be considered for future work: hexagons.

On the numerical side, the integration of adaptive mesh refinement could significantly improve the efficiency of the method by concentrating computational resources on dynamically active regions such as fronts or jets. Similarly, the use of compatible higher-order finite elements or hybrid discretisations can improve the accuracy and convergence properties of the model, especially for long-term integrations. The use of other time-stepping methods, in addition to the explicit Runge-Kutta method we use, can also be an interesting approach. Here we refer to the work of BAUER AND COTTER [BC25]. Besides this, the appendix contains a short summary of THOMAS BENDALL's [BCS19] work, which describes a possible recovery procedure. Another alternative is provided here by the work of VOGEL AND KNOTH [VK22]. However, further work should first be done on parallelisation

and efficiency improvement of the code. This can then serve as a foundation for further research.

In terms of software and computational performance, extending the current Julia-based implementation toward high-performance computing (HPC) environments would enable large-scale simulations required for operational weather and climate models. This includes parallelisation strategies, GPU acceleration, and integration with existing HPC libraries and solvers. The advantage would be a much faster and more efficient way of simulating large Earth system models.

Finally, applying the developed framework to practical test cases, such as idealised climate scenarios or data assimilation experiments, would offer valuable insights into the real-world applicability and robustness of the method. Here, it is worth mentioning DCMIP-25 once again, which provides a great opportunity to network and connect young climate scientists and mathematicians from all over the world. The advantages of finite volume methods are obvious. However, finite element methods can be used to do preliminary work and explore scientific basics. The combination with machine learning is interesting, as it could once again be a game-changer in climate and weather research. All these efforts could also serve as a springboard for developing the next generation of Earth system models.

Appendix A

Quadrature rules of triangular elements

Within the work, we realised that good quadrature rules, specifically for triangles, are not entirely easy to define, and we should dedicate a little more time and effort to selecting a robust choice. In our numerical implementation, we use the work of KUBATKO [Kub25]. After several tests, the following non-product rule has proven to be advantageous, which we have implemented up to order 6.

Lemma A.0.1 (Non-Product Quadrature Rule for Triangles). *Let $T \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be the reference triangle with vertices at $(-1, -1)$, $(1, -1)$, $(-1, 1)$. Then there exists a quadrature rule of the form*

$$\int_T f(x, y) dx dy \approx \sum_{i=1}^N w_i f(x_i, y_i),$$

such that the following properties hold:

1. **Non-product nature:** The nodes (x_i, y_i) and weights w_i are not derived from tensor-product rules, but are constructed specifically for the triangular geometry.
2. **Interior points only:** All quadrature nodes (x_i, y_i) lie strictly in the interior of T , i.e.,

$$(x_i, y_i) \in \text{int}(T), \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N.$$

This avoids placing nodes on edges or vertices, simplifying the numerical implementation.

3. **Symmetry and efficiency:** The quadrature rule exploits the geometric symmetry of the triangle and achieves exact integration for all polynomials of total degree less than or equal to a given order k , using a minimal number of nodes.
4. **Polynomial exactness:** There exists such a rule for any integer $k \geq 1$, such that the approximation is exact for all $f \in \mathbb{P}_k$, the space of polynomials of total degree at most k .

(a) 3-point, degree $k = 2$

(b) 6-point, degree $k = 4$

(c) 12-point, degree $k = 6$

Figure A.1: In our default setting in CGDYCORE.JL we are using the 6-point rule, degree $k = 4$. of KUBATKO [Kub25].

Appendix B

Grid-Output Refinement

To generate even more detailed and improved output, we have refined the grid once again. To achieve this, we either halved or tripled the number of grid cells. The method is explained quite simply. We cut the individual edges in half or thirds and connect the points to generate a grid refinement. You can see this in the following pictures.

Figure B.1: Triangle and quadrilateral refinement

If we now place these individual reference elements in a larger grid section and join them together, we obtain the following image:

Remark B.0.1. The entire code is published in [SSK25] and you can find the latest version on Github.

Figure B.2: Triangular grid with refine level 1

Literature

- [Bar16] S. Bartels. *Numerical Approximation of Partial Differential Equations*. Texts in Applied Mathematics. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2016.
- [BC25] W. Bauer and C. J. Cotter. *Fully implicit timestepping methods for the rotating shallow water equations*. Aug. 4, 2025.
- [BCS19] T. M. Bendall, C. J. Cotter, and J. Shipton. “The ‘recovered space’ advection scheme for lowest-order compatible finite element methods”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 390 (Aug. 2019), pp. 342–358.
- [Bre10] S. Brenner. *The mathematical theory of finite element methods*. Softcover reprint of hardcover 3rd ed. 2008. Texts in applied mathematics ; 15. Springer-Verlag New York Inc., 2010.
- [BF91] F. Brezzi and M. Fortin, eds. *Mixed and Hybrid Finite Element Methods*. Springer Series in Computational Mathematics. New York, NY: Springer, 1991.
- [CFN50] J. Charney, R. Fjörtoft, and J. Neumann. “Numerical Integration of the Barotropic Vorticity Equation”. In: *Tellus A* 2 (Nov. 1, 1950).
- [CW20] X. Chen and D. M. Williams. “Versatile mixed methods for the incompressible Navier–Stokes equations”. In: *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* 80.6 (Sept. 15, 2020), pp. 1555–1577.
- [CM14] C. J. Cotter and A. T. T. McRae. *Compatible finite element methods for numerical weather prediction*. Jan. 3, 2014.
- [CK16] C. Cotter and D. Kuzmin. “Embedded discontinuous Galerkin transport schemes with localised limiters”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 311 (Apr. 2016), pp. 363–373.
- [DM08] C. Dawson and C. M. Mirabito. “The Shallow Water Equations”. Institute for Computational Engineering and Sciences, University of Texas, Austin, Sept. 29, 2008.
- [Eng23] E. Engheim. *Julia as a Second Language: General purpose programming with a taste of data science*. New York: Manning Publications, 2023. 1 p.
- [EG21] A. Ern and J.-L. Guermond. *Finite elements I: approximation and interpolation*. Texts in applied mathematics volume 72. Cham: Springer, 2021. 1 p.

- [Etl08] D. Etling. *Theoretische Meteorologie: Eine Einführung*. 3. erw. u. aktualisierte Aufl. 2008. SpringerLink ; Bücher. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2008. 1 p.
- [Eva10] L. C. Evans. *Partial differential equations*. 2. ed. Graduate studies in mathematics, 19. American Mathematical Society, 2010.
- [GSP04] J. Galewsky, R. K. Scott, and L. M. Polvani. “An initial-value problem for testing numerical models of the global shallow-water equations”. In: *Tellus A* 56.5 (2004), pp. 429–440.
- [Han56] W. Hansen. “Theorie zur Errechnung des Wasserstandes und der Strömungen in Randmeeren nebst Anwendungen”. In: *Tellus* 8.3 (Aug. 1956), pp. 287–300.
- [Kub25] Kubatko. *quadtriangle*. July 19, 2025. URL: <https://de.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/72131-quadtriangle> (visited on 07/19/2025).
- [LB13] M. G. Larson and F. Bengzon. *The Finite Element Method: Theory, Implementation, and Applications*. Vol. 10. Texts in Computational Science and Engineering. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2013.
- [Lin+17] S.-J. Lin et al. “Colliding Modons: A Nonlinear Test for the Evaluation of Global Dynamical Cores”. In: *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 9.7 (2017), pp. 2483–2492.
- [McL22] K. L. McLain. “Finite Element Methods for the Shallow Water Equations”. MA thesis. Freie Universität Berlin, 2022.
- [PF03] F. J. Poulin and G. R. Flierl. “The Nonlinear Evolution of Barotropically Unstable Jets”. In: *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 33.10 (Oct. 1, 2003), pp. 2173–2192.
- [Rog+13] M. E. Rognes et al. “Automating the solution of PDEs on the sphere and other manifolds in FEniCS 1.2”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 6.6 (Dec. 17, 2013), pp. 2099–2119.
- [RIP96] C. Ronchi, R. Iacono, and P. S. Paolucci. “The ‘‘Cubed Sphere’’: A New Method for the Solution of Partial Differential Equations in Spherical Geometry”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 124.1 (Mar. 1, 1996), pp. 93–114.
- [SSK25] L. Seifert, M. Schedensack, and O. Knoth. “A finite element approach for solving the shallow water equation on the sphere”. Diploma thesis. Leipzig University, Aug. 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16910651.
- [SGC18] J. Shipton, T. Gibson, and C. Cotter. “Higher-order compatible finite element schemes for the nonlinear rotating shallow water equations on the sphere”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 375 (Dec. 2018), pp. 1121–1137.

- [Tom+01] H. Tomita et al. “Shallow Water Model on a Modified Icosahedral Geodesic Grid by Using Spring Dynamics”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 174.2 (Dec. 10, 2001), pp. 579–613.
- [VK22] D. Vogel and O. Knoth. “High-Order Polynomial Recovery in Finite Element Advection Schemes”. In: May 1, 2022, pp. 93–120.
- [Vre94] C. B. Vreugdenhil. *Numerical Methods for Shallow-Water Flow*. Water Science and Technology Library v.13. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 1994. 1 p.
- [Wei92] T. Weiyan. “Shallow Water Hydrodynamics”. In: *Elsevier Oceanography Series*. Vol. 55. Elsevier, 1992, p. iii.
- [Wil+92] D. L. Williamson et al. “A standard test set for numerical approximations to the shallow water equations in spherical geometry”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 102.1 (Sept. 1992), pp. 211–224.

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